

TEACHERS' RESILIENCE AND WORK PERFORMANCE DURING THE NEW NORMAL: BASIS FOR TEACHERS' LEARNING AND DEVELOPMENT

Jomar A. Mariano, LPT, Ph.D.

*Isabela School of Arts and Trades, Department of Education,
City of Ilagan, Isabela, Philippines.*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12794375>

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the resilience and work performance of Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc teachers in the City of Ilagan during the new normal, using a descriptive-correlational design. The research, conducted in four Technical-Vocational and six Non-Technical-Vocational schools, involved 314 teachers selected through simple random sampling. Data were gathered via questionnaires, documentary analysis, and informal interviews. Findings reveal that most teachers are middle-aged, female, married, with master's units and short tenures. They exhibit high resilience, particularly in personal competencies, family cohesion, social skills, peer support, and spiritual influences. Work performance across both groups is outstanding in task and contextual performance, work behavior, and all key result areas of the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF), except for the Learning Environment. Performance significantly varies with age, sex, civil status, educational background, position, and years in service, notably in KRA 2. Recommendations include sustaining teacher resilience through support and mentoring, encouraging capacity-building seminars, and reviewing the learning and development program to enhance resilience and performance. Further research is suggested to explore additional factors affecting resilience and instructional performance.

Keywords: *Resilience, Work Performance, Tech-Voc teachers, New Normal, Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF), Descriptive-Correlational Design*

INTRODUCTION

In all parts of the world, education takes a great role for it is regarded as the major catalyst to fill the minds with vital knowledge and wisdom among all learners. It becomes the bridge to successfully reach one's destination towards fulfilling goals of realizing enormous dreams, making it possible for a dreamer to have that open door of greater opportunities. Truly, education is a compass that paves the way towards progression and aids ignorance in inscribing such reality in life. Schools have the key responsibility to cater to the significant educational needs of learners with an atmosphere conducive to learning. Thus, teachers become the educational frontline and prime movers in the educative process.

During the new normal, the Department of Education implemented the Basic Education-Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) where in-person classes and distance learning delivery modalities were set up and adopted during the first quarter of the school year 2022-2023. Yet, during the second quarter, full face-to-face classes were conducted to make learning much more meaningful to all learners after two years of being in a virtual room and a modular setup. Health protocol is still observed through the voluntary use of face masks, but it is still encouraged to use while the locality is still battling a health crisis. School administrators, teachers, and parents work in strong collaboration to keep all learners safe when going to school.

It is further observed that during this new normal in education, many teachers were confronted with challenges in terms of lesson delivery which consists of lesson planning, crafting of up-to-date daily lesson logs (DLL) aligned with the most essential learning competencies (MELCs) imposed by the department and making interactive educational and instructional materials. The teacher's move scheme is considered for the benefit of learners. The student population has increased, therefore, there is a lack of classrooms resulting in double shifts among teachers to accommodate all learners. This has also resulted in a lack of teachers. Adding to their duties, remedial classes are done for struggling students.

Primary classroom duties and responsibilities such as classroom management, student engagement, related works outside teaching, work issues and the pressing work demands, and personal matters such as family responsibilities, finances, and health problems have become the stressors confronting educators today. Such scenarios experienced by them test their patience and resilience at work, which can also affect their overall instructional performance in the new normal, and the new setup in the educational system while still amidst the COVID-19 pandemic.

Indeed, the most esteemed profession in the world is that of a teacher (Strauss, 2018). They were important long before COVID-19, but perhaps it will take a pandemic to finally recognize their contributions and the challenges they are facing (Dabrowski, 2020). Like anyone else, educators face multifarious battles that test their resilience and work performance, especially in this new normal.

In relation to this study, Fonte et al. (2021) concluded that during the implementation of the distance learning delivery modality, teachers were very resilient at work, their work performance was very satisfactory, and their level of resilience affected their work performance. This makes a clearer perspective that teachers with a high degree of resiliency will heighten their instructional performance.

Hence, the researcher, being a Technical-Vocational School teacher, was prompted and motivated to explore, conduct, and pursue this study to purposely determine the teachers' resilience level and their work performance during the new normal focusing on Technical-Vocational and Non-Technical-Vocational Schools. Additionally, he also sought to find out if significant differences in the resilience level and work performance of the aforementioned schools exist as basis for a proposed learning and development activities that will heighten teachers' resilience and work performance, especially in this new normal education.

Through readings of related literature and studies, and based on the available research and published literature, no study yet has been made on the relationship of the profile, resilience level, and work performance in Technical-Vocational and Non-Technical-Vocational Schools in the country, hence, this study entitled Teachers' Resilience and Work Performance During the New Normal: Basis for Teachers' Learning and Development.

Conceptual Framework

Teachers are the focal stakeholders and prime movers of the educative process. It is imperative to figure out the factors affecting their performance. This study anchors itself on the concept of Fonte, et al. (2021) that when teachers demonstrate a high resilience at work, better work performance is expected.

It is noted that when teachers are resilient, despite the ever-changing contexts and situations where they work, they are likely to be able to sustain their quality teaching performance. Daniilidou and Platsidou (2018) identified factors affecting teachers' resilience which consist of the following components: *Personal Competencies and Persistence* describe the personal qualities that affect resilience and tenacity; *Family Cohesion* refers to the relationship of the individuals to their family, which can act as a protective factor of resilience; *Social Skills and Peer Support* refer to the relationship of the individuals with their colleagues in the school context and the ability to form new relationships in their professional environment; and *Spiritual Influences* refer to the need of the individual to seek help from God or other spiritual forces to deal with the challenges.

On the other hand, Koopmans et al. (2013) claim that work performance is very important in determining consistency and maintaining employee work resilience. Work performance is a behavior or action associated with the organization's goals. Individual work performance consists of task performance, contextual performance, and work behavior. Task performance is the proficiency with which individuals perform the core substantive or technical tasks central to his or her job (Campbell, 1990), while contextual

performance is the degree to which individuals engage in activities that contribute to organizational effectiveness in ways that shape the organizational, social, and psychological context that catalyzes task activities (Borman and Motowidlo, 1997).

Moreover, DepEd public school teachers are guided by the Results-based Performance Management System - Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (RPMS-IPCRF) which is composed of Key Result Areas (KRA) 1 to 5 with specific objectives that have to be attained throughout the school year.

Indeed, by heightening the level of resilience, teachers' instructional performance is expected to improve, thus, resulting in effective and efficient classroom teaching.

Research Questions

The study explored the teacher's resilience and work performance during the new normal as a basis for teacher's learning and development.

Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of teacher-respondents in terms of the following:
 - a. age
 - b. sex
 - c. civil status
 - d. educational attainment
 - e. teaching position
 - f. length of service
2. What is the respondents' level of resilience as to:
 - a. personal competencies and persistence
 - b. family cohesion
 - c. social skills and peer support
 - d. spiritual influences
3. Is there a significant difference in respondents' level of resilience when grouped according to their profile?
4. Is there a significant difference in Technical-Vocational and Non-Technical-Vocational School teachers' level of resilience?
5. What is the respondents' level of work performance in terms of:
 - a. task performance
 - b. contextual performance
 - c. work behavior
 - d. IPCRF Key Result Areas
6. Is there a significant difference in the respondents' level of work performance when grouped according to their profile?
7. Is there a significant difference in Technical-Vocational and Non-Technical-Vocational School teachers' level of work performance?
8. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' resilience and their work performance?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The descriptive method using the survey and correlation techniques was used in the study. Descriptive-correlational design, according to Becker et al. (2016), is used to explain the phenomena, attitudes, opinions, behaviors, or other defined variables by collecting numerical data which are analyzed using statistically based methods.

Since this study dwelt on determining the teacher's resilience, work performance, and its significant relationship between and among variables, this design is deemed most appropriate.

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted in the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan, particularly in four Technical-Vocational Schools and six Non-Technical-Vocational Schools. The Technical-Vocational Schools consist of the Isabela School of Arts and Trades (ISAT) – Main located in Calamagui 2nd, the Isabela School of Arts and Trades (ISAT) – Cabannungan Annex located in Cabannungan 1st, San Rafael National and Vocational High School (SRNVHS) in Cabisera 17-21, and San Antonio National Agro-Industrial and Vocational High School (SANAIVHS) located in San Antonio. These Tech-Voc Schools in the City offer Tech-Voc subjects/specializations that hone students' specific knowledge and skills. The Non-Technical-Vocational (National High) Schools are composed of the Isabela National High School located in San Vicente Poblacion, Alibagu National High School in Alibagu, Ilagan West National High School in Naguillan Baculud, Santa Isabel National High School in Santa Isabel Sur, Rang-ayan National High School in Rang-ayan, and Abuan National High School in Cabisera 27.

Selection and Description of Respondents

The respondents of this study include 132 teachers from the Technical-Vocational Schools and 182 teachers from the Non-Technical-Vocational Schools in the Division of the City of Ilagan.

Simple random sampling was utilized to determine the respondents in each identified school. Slovin's Formula was employed to determine the sample size.

Data Gathering Instruments

The study made use of questionnaires as the main instrument to gather the needed data supplemented by documentary analysis and informal interviews.

Questionnaire. A four-part questionnaire was used to obtain information on the respondents' profile, level of resilience, individual work performance, and their IPCRF.

Part I: This consists of items related to the respondents' profile such as age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, teaching position, and length of service.

Part II: This was intended to measure the teachers' resilience using the Teachers' Resilience Scale developed by Daniilidou and Platsidou (2018). The questionnaire is divided into four components: personal competencies and persistence, family cohesion, social skills and peer support, and spiritual influences.

Part III: This was intended to determine the work performance of teachers using the Individual Work Performance Questionnaire (IWPQ) developed by Koopmans et al. (2014). It consists of items in relation to task performance, contextual performance, and work behavior, respectively.

Modifications were made in both TRS and IWPQ to align the statements with the new normal.

Documentary Analysis. This consists of Part IV: IPCRF Key Result Areas. This was used to measure the individual performance of teachers using the objectives in each KRA through self-assessment by the respondents.

Informal Interview. This was done to reaffirm and validate the answers of respondents in the questionnaires given.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher asked permission from the office of the Schools Division Superintendent, City of Ilagan Division through a letter of request to conduct the study in its Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc Schools. Thereafter, upon approval, the researcher coordinated with the school heads and head teachers informing them of the objectives and process of the study. After proper coordination was made, the researcher personally floated, distributed, administered, and retrieved the questionnaires accomplished by the target respondents. He also conducted informal interviews and conversations with the respondents while retrieving the questionnaires. Health protocols were strictly followed during the process.

Data Analysis Procedure

To determine the teachers' level of resilience, the five-point Likert scale was used as follows:

<u>Weight</u>	<u>Mean Range</u>	<u>Response</u>	<u>Level of Resilience</u>
5	4.20-5.00	Always	Very High
4	3.40-4.19	Often	High
3	2.60-3.39	Sometimes	Moderate
2	1.80-2.59	Rarely	Low
1	1.00-1.79	Never	Very Low

To assess the teachers' work performance in terms of task and contextual performance, the five-point Likert scale was applied as follows:

Weight	Mean Range	Response	Work Performance
5	4.20-5.00	Always	Outstanding
4	3.40-4.19	Often	Very Satisfactory
3	2.60-3.39	Sometimes	Satisfactory
2	1.80-2.59	Rarely	Unsatisfactory
1	1.00-1.79	Never	Poor

To evaluate the teachers' work behavior, the five-point Likert scale was employed as follows:

Weight	Mean Range	Response	Work Behavior
5	4.20-5.00	Always	Poor
4	3.40-4.19	Often	Unsatisfactory
3	2.60-3.39	Sometimes	Satisfactory
2	1.80-2.59	Rarely	Very Satisfactory
1	1.00-1.79	Never	Outstanding

To appraise the teachers' work performance in terms of IPCRF key result areas, the five-point Likert scale was utilized as follows:

Weight	Mean Range	Response	IPCRF Performance
5	4.20-5.00	Always	Outstanding
4	3.40-4.19	Often	Very Satisfactory
3	2.60-3.39	Sometimes	Satisfactory
2	1.80-2.59	Rarely	Unsatisfactory
1	1.00-1.79	Never	Poor

The classification of different items of the Teachers' Resilience Scale (TRS) is presented below:

Teachers' Resilience	Items
A. Personal Competencies and Persistence	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9
B. Family Cohesion	10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15
C. Social Skills and Peer Support	16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23
D. Spiritual Influences	24, 25, 26

The classification of different items of Individual Work Performance Questionnaires (IWPQ) is shown below:

Individual Work Performance	Items
Task Performance	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7
Contextual Performance	8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19

Work Behavior	20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27
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The classification of different items of IPCRF key result areas objectives are presented below:

KRA	Items
KRA 1 - Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	1, 2, 3, 4
KRA 2 - Learning Environment	5, 6, 7, 8
KRA 3 - Diversity of Learners, Curriculum and Planning, and Assessment and Reporting	9, 10, 11, 12
KRA 4 - Community Linkages and Professional Engagement and Personal Growth and Professional Development	13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18
KRA 5 - Plus Factor	19

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Respondents' Profile

Table 1. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents According to Age

Age	Tech-Voc School Teachers		Non-Tech-Voc School Teachers	
	Frequency (<i>f</i>)	Percentage (%)	Frequency (<i>f</i>)	Percentage (%)
21-25	10	7.58	14	7.69
26-30	44	33.33	53	29.12
31-35	25	18.94	21	11.54
36-40	23	17.42	26	14.29
41-45	18	13.64	20	10.99
46-50	6	4.55	21	11.54
51-55	4	3.03	13	7.14
56-60	2	1.52	12	6.59
61-65	0	0.00	2	1.10
Total	132	100.00	182	100.00

Table 1 illustrates the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents according to their age. Majority of the Tech-Voc School teachers belong to the age group of 26-30 years with a total of 44 or 33.33 percent, followed by 31-35 years old with 25 or 18.94 percent, 36-40 age group with 23 or 17.42 percent, 18 or 13.64 percent come from 41-45 years age bracket, while 10 or 7.58 percent go to 21-25 years of age. Only two or 1.52 percent belong to 56-60 years old which got the lowest frequency.

On the other hand, for the Non-Tech-Voc School teachers, 53 or 29.12 of the total respondents come from the age group of 26-30 years. Those in the age group of 36-40 years are comprised of 26 or 14.29 percent, followed by age group 31-35 and 46-50 with 21 or 11.54 percent. Only two or 1.10 percent belong to 61-65 years old which was the least number of respondents.

It can be surmised that the teachers are in their prime age. It is worthy to note that there are teachers who are still in the service at the age of 61-65 which may manifest their passion and dedication in their professional work to impart essential knowledge to every learner.

Table 2. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents According to Sex

Sex	Tech-Voc School Teachers		Non-Tech-Voc School Teachers	
	Frequency (<i>f</i>)	Percentage (%)	Frequency (<i>f</i>)	Percentage (%)
Male	48	36.36	41	22.53
Female	84	63.64	141	77.47
Total	132	100.00	182	100.00

Table 2 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents according to sex. As revealed, Tech-Voc School is dominated by females with 84 or 63.64 percent whereas 36.36 percent or 48 are male teacher-respondents. Meanwhile, Non-Tech-Voc School also has the highest composition of female teachers with 141 or 77.47 percent compared to 41 or 22.53 male teachers.

Truly, in the education sector, there is no doubt that female teachers dominate the population as commonly observed.

Table 3. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents According to Civil Status

Civil Status	Tech-Voc School Teachers		Non-Tech-Voc School Teachers	
	Frequency (<i>f</i>)	Percentage (%)	Frequency (<i>f</i>)	Percentage (%)
Single	42	31.82	41	22.53
Married	89	67.42	137	75.27
Widowed	1	0.76	4	2.20
Total	132	100.00	182	100.00

Table 3 exhibits the civil status frequency and percentage distribution of respondents. More than half of the total or 67.42 percent of Tech-Voc School teachers are married, 42, or 31.82 are single, and only one, or 0.76 percent is widowed. Similarly, most of the teacher-respondents from the Non-Tech-Voc Schools are married with 75.27 percent, followed by single individuals with 41 or 22.53 percent, and just 4 or 2.20 of them are widowed.

It can be inferred that being married and having a family is a part of every individual's life. Furthermore, family is the reason why individuals work for them to sustain a living.

Table 4. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents According to Highest Educational Attainment

Highest Educational Attainment	Tech-Voc School Teachers		Non-Tech-Voc School Teachers	
	Frequency (<i>f</i>)	Percentage (%)	Frequency (<i>f</i>)	Percentage (%)
Bachelor's Degree	15	11.36	29	15.93
Master's Units	93	70.45	110	60.44
Master's Degree	19	14.39	34	18.68
Doctorate Units	4	3.03	8	4.40
Doctorate Degree	1	0.76	1	0.55
Total	132	100.00	182	100.00

Table 4 discloses the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents' highest educational attainment. Of the 132 Tech-Voc School teachers, 93 or 70.45 percent have earned master's units, followed by 19 or 14.39 percent with a master's degree, 15, or 11.36 percent have a bachelor's degree, while four or 3.03 percent have doctorate units. One or 0.76 percent possesses a doctorate. For the Non-Tech-Voc teachers, more than half, or 60.44 percent have master's units, followed by 34, or 18.68 percent with a master's degree, 29 or 15.93 percent have attained a bachelor's degree, while eight, or 4.40 percent took have doctorate units. One or 0.55 percent has completed his/her doctorate.

As revealed in the table, most of the teachers are engaged in continuing professional development by upgrading themselves through graduate and post-graduate studies to enrich their knowledge and skills especially in these changing and challenging times of the 21st century. This surfaced during informal conversations of the researcher with the respondents.

Table 5. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents According to Teaching Position

Teaching Position	Tech-Voc School Teachers		Non-Tech-Voc School Teachers	
	Frequency (<i>f</i>)	Percentage (%)	Frequency (<i>f</i>)	Percentage (%)
Teacher 1	33	25.00	37	20.33
Teacher 2	8	6.06	29	15.93
Teacher 3	84	63.64	100	54.95
Master Teacher 1	6	4.55	12	6.59

Master Teacher 2	1	0.76	4	2.20
Total	132	100.00	182	100.00

Table 5 displays the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents according to teaching position. Among the Tech-Voc School teachers, 63.64 percent hold the position of Teacher 3, 25.00 percent, or 33 are Teacher 1, eight or 6.06 percent are Teacher 2, and six or 4.55 percent are Master Teacher 1. Only one or 0.76 percent got the Master Teacher 2 position. As regards the Non-Tech-Voc teachers, there are 54.95 percent hold the Teacher 3 position, 20.33 percent or 37 are Teacher 1, 15.93 percent or 29 are Teacher 2, 6.59 or 12 are Master Teacher 1, while four or 2.20 percent hold the position of Master Teacher 2.

The biggest number in both groups of respondents are those with Teacher 3 positions. They are promoted from Teacher 1 either by filling up vacancies or through reclassification. Reclassification of teachers is made possible through the Equivalents Record Form (ERF) under Section 14 of Presidential Decree No. 985, as long as the applicants meet the requirements of 36 M.A. units or 33 M.A. units plus 150 hours of seminar or training attended. On the other hand, a small number of Master Teachers is expected due to the guideline that an allotment of one MT position per subject area for at least 5-7 teachers should be the basis in the secondary level, pursuant to DECS Order No. 70, s. 1998.

Table 6. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents According to Length of Service

Length of Service	Tech-Voc School Teachers		Non-Tech-Voc School Teachers	
	Frequency (<i>f</i>)	Percentage (%)	Frequency (<i>f</i>)	Percentage (%)
1-5 Yrs.	46	34.85	64	35.16
6-10 Yrs.	57	43.18	41	22.53
11-15 Yrs.	20	15.15	28	15.38
16-20 Yrs.	5	3.79	14	7.69
21-25 Yrs.	0	0.00	11	6.04
26-30 Yrs.	2	1.52	14	7.69
31-35 Yrs.	2	1.52	8	4.40
36-40 Yrs.	0	0.00	2	1.10
Total	132	100.00	182	100.00

Table 6 unveils the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents' length of service. Most of the Tech-Voc School teachers are 6-10 years in the service with 57 or 43.18 percent, followed by 1-5 years with 46 or 34.85 percent, 11-15 years with 20 or 15.15 percent, 16-20 years with five or 3.79 percent, while two or 1.52 percent have served for about 26-30 years and 31-35 years. Regarding the length of service of Non-Tech-Voc School teachers, 1-5 years got the greatest number of respondents with 64 or 35.16 percent, followed by 6-10 years with 41 or 22.53 percent, 11-15 years with 28 or

15.38 percent, and two or 1.10 percent have been in the service for about 36-40 years now.

Many teacher-respondents are new in the service in public schools. These teachers were hired at a young age, yet as observed, some teachers came from private institutions who applied and got hired in public schools.

2. Respondents' Level of Resilience

a. Personal Competencies and Persistence

Table 7. Respondents' Level of Resilience in Terms of Personal Competencies and Persistence

Personal Competencies and Persistence	Tech-Voc School Teachers		Non-Tech-Voc School Teachers	
	Weighted Mean	Description	Weighted Mean	Description
1. I think of myself as a strong person.	4.46	Very High	4.48	Very High
2. If necessary, I can make unpopular or difficult decisions that affect others.	3.39	Moderate	3.47	High
3. I am not easily discouraged by failure.	4.02	High	4.11	High
4. I like challenges.	3.92	High	4.15	High
5. I can handle unpleasant feelings, such as anger or fear.	3.95	High	3.95	High
6. Under pressure, I am able to focus and think clearly.	3.81	High	3.98	High
7. I prefer to take the lead in problem-solving.	3.54	High	3.72	High
8. I work hard to attain my goals.	4.58	Very High	4.67	Very High
9. I am able to adapt to change.	4.51	Very High	4.60	Very High
Category Mean	4.02	High	4.13	High

Table 7 reveals the respondents' level of resilience in terms of personal competencies and persistence. As presented, both Tech-Voc School teachers and Non-Tech-Voc School teachers have a mean of 4.02 and 4.13 respectively which explicitly indicate that in this domain, they possess a *high* resilience.

Specifically, both Tech-Voc School teachers and Non-Tech-Voc School teachers hold a *very high* resilience for the following specific indicators: "They work hard to attain their goals with weighted means of 4.58 and 4.67, able to adapt to change with 4.51 and 4.60 and think of themselves as a strong person" with 4.46 and 4.48, respectively. However, it is interesting to note that there is a difference in the statement, "if necessary, they can make unpopular or difficult decisions that affect others" where Tech-Voc School teachers *sometimes* do it described as *moderate*, whereas the Non-Tech-Voc School

teachers claim they *often* do it, interpreted as *high*. Meanwhile, this same statement yields the lowest weighted mean for both Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc respondents.

It can be deduced that teachers have gained personal competencies and persistence through their personal and professional experiences. Indeed, they experience failures but they can stand firm, face such challenges with courage, and able to adapt to changes with endurance. This came out during the informal interview among teachers. Relatively, Patterson, Collins, and Abbott (2004) revealed that resilient teachers have a set of personal values that guide their decision-making.

b. Family Cohesion

Table 8. Respondents' Level of Resilience in Terms of Family Cohesion

Family Cohesion	Tech-Voc School Teachers		Non-Tech-Voc School Teachers	
	Weighted Mean	Description	Weighted Mean	Description
1. My family is characterized by healthy coherence.	4.48	Very High	4.44	Very High
2. I feel very happy with my family.	4.81	Very High	4.84	Very High
3. In my family, we like to do things together.	4.63	Very High	4.76	Very High
4. In difficult periods my family keeps a positive outlook on the future.	4.55	Very High	4.45	Very High
5. Facing other people, our family acts loyal towards one another.	4.56	Very High	4.48	Very High
6. My family's understanding of what is important in life is very similar to mine.	4.53	Very High	4.48	Very High
Category Mean	4.59	Very High	4.58	Very High

Table 8 illustrates the respondents' level of resilience in terms of family cohesion. As shown, both Tech-Voc School teachers and Non-Tech-Voc School teachers got a mean of 4.59 and 4.58 correspondingly which implies that in this domain, they possess a *very high* resilience.

Noticeably, Tech-Voc School teachers got weighted mean values ranging from 4.48 to 4.81 while the Non-Tech-Voc School teachers garnered weighted mean responses ranging from 4.44 to 4.84 which describes that all the items in this category are demonstrated by the respondents to a *very high* level.

Hence, teachers do get strength and inspiration from their families for them to become much more resilient during their tough battles, personal or in their workplace as professionals. This was confirmed by the respondents during the informal conversations. Botou et al. (2017) asserted the importance of family in building resilience. They found

that the strong family nexus helped teachers in Greece maintain their resilience during the economic crisis.

c. Social Skills and Peer Support

Table 9. Respondents' Level of Resilience in Terms of Social Skills and Peer Support

Social Skills and Peer Support	Tech-Voc School Teachers		Non-Tech-Voc School Teachers	
	Weighted Mean	Description	Weighted Mean	Description
1. New friendships are something I make easily in my workplace.	4.25	Very High	4.26	Very High
2. The bonds between my peers and me are strong.	4.30	Very High	4.31	Very High
3. I get support from my peers.	4.41	Very High	4.43	Very High
4. Meeting new people in my workplace is something I am good at.	4.23	Very High	4.16	High
5. When needed, I have always someone in my workplace who can help me.	4.35	Very High	4.45	Very High
6. I can discuss personal issues with my peers.	3.70	High	3.72	High
7. In my workplace when I am with other people, I easily laugh.	4.27	Very High	4.16	High
8. In my workplace I enjoy being together with other people.	4.15	High	4.20	Very High
Category Mean	4.21	Very High	4.21	Very High

Table 9 displays the respondents' level of resilience in terms of social skills and peer support. Tech-Voc School teachers are *always* "good at meeting new people in their workplace", with a weighted mean of 4.23 described as having *very high* resilience, whereas the Non-Tech-Voc School teachers are *often* good at it, with a weighted mean of 4.16, or *high* resilience. Tech-Voc School teachers *always* "easily laugh in their workplace when they are with other people" with a weighted mean of 4.27 described as *very high*, whereas Non-Tech-Voc School teachers *often* easily laugh with others, with 4.16 inferred as *high*. Tech-voc school teachers *often* and Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers *always* "enjoy being together with other people in the workplace" with 4.15 described as *high* and 4.20 marked as *very high* resilience, respectively.

Moreover, both Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers say they *always* get support from their peers which got the highest weighted means of 4.41 and 4.43 respectively, interpreted as having *very high* resilience. Meanwhile, these groups of teachers say that they *often* "discuss personal issues with their peers" whom they trusted the most. This item got the lowest weighted means of 3.70 and 3.72 respectively, inferred as *high*.

Remarkably, both Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers got the same mean of 4.21 which infers that in this domain, they possess a *very high* resilience.

Indeed, teachers greatly manifest and possess a very high level of resilience through socialization and when getting genuine support from their peers in their place of work. Building camaraderie, strong bonds, and extended arms to help one another become the ingredients to build stronger resilience for individuals to get up from any adversity. In relation to this, Bobek (2002) stressed that to foster resilience, new teachers must seek out relationships with colleagues who understand teaching and what teachers do.

d. Spiritual Influences

Table 10. Respondents' Level of Resilience in Terms of Spiritual Influences

Spiritual Influences	Tech-Voc School Teachers		Non-Tech-Voc School Teachers	
	Weighted Mean	Description	Weighted Mean	Description
1. God or fate can help me overcome challenges.	4.84	Very High	4.82	Very High
2. I believe things happen for a reason.	4.78	Very High	4.77	Very High
3. I believe I have to act on a hunch (strong intuitive feeling).	4.45	Very High	4.49	Very High
Category Mean	4.69	Very High	4.69	Very High

Table 10 depicts the respondents' level of resilience in terms of spiritual influences. Both Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc School teachers got the same mean of 4.69 which indicates that in this domain, they possess a *very high* resilience.

Tech-Voc School teachers got weighted mean values ranging from 4.45 to 4.84 while the Non-Tech-Voc School teachers garnered weighted mean responses ranging from 4.49 to 4.82 which describes that all the items in this category demonstrated by both groups of respondents to a *very high* level.

During the informal interview, teachers confirm that they do rely on a Supreme Being who is the mediator of their lives. They know that at the end of the day, they could be able to overcome challenges through their faith. They also believe that things happen for a purpose. Hence, by depending on spiritual influences, teachers become much more strongly resilient personally and professionally.

Moreover, the results assert Ang and Diaz' (2014) findings that most of the participants strongly believe that there is God who would help them recover from calamities and other misfortunes. The resiliency of the people as provided by the respondents would often be faith-based. Yet, Ignacio (2011) emphasized that this

spirituality allows their resilience to come forth in times of crises and extreme life experiences.

Table 11. Summary of the Respondents' Level of Resilience

Resilience	Tech-Voc School Teachers		Non-Tech-Voc School Teachers	
	Weighted Mean	Description	Weighted Mean	Description
a. Personal Competencies and Persistence	4.02	High	4.13	High
b. Family Cohesion	4.59	Very High	4.58	Very High
c. Social Skills and Peer Support	4.21	Very High	4.21	Very High
d. Spiritual Influences	4.69	Very High	4.69	Very High
Overall Mean	4.38	Very High	4.40	Very High

Table 11 reveals the summary of the respondents' level of resilience. As shown in the table, both Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc School teachers acquired the same *high* level of personal competencies and persistence with weighted means of 4.02 and 4.13, respectively. Also, they hold a *very high* level of resilience along the other three domains family cohesion, social skills and peer support, and spiritual influences. Overall, both groups possess a *very high* level of resilience.

As shown, the respondents possess a high and very high level of resilience. This is confirmed by Amin et al. (2022) in which they found out that most of the teachers are classified as having high and very high resilience and none as low or very low resilience.

Teachers' level of resilience is optimum despite the challenging situation they are facing during the new normal. Relative to this note, Gibbs and Miller (2014) contended that lecturers are resilient and there should not be too much worry about their commitment to their teaching. They are very likely to be able to adapt to the new teaching situation.

Chan (2008) suggested training on personal skills such as stress management for building resilience among teachers. Tait (2008) reported that ingraining socialization skills, assertiveness, self-discipline, and empathy may improve the resilience of teachers.

Furthermore, Day and Gu (2010) specified that personal characteristics, competencies, and positive influences of the social environment in which the individual works and lives, independently and together interact to contribute to the process of resilience building.

3. Significant Difference Between the Respondents' Level of Resilience When Grouped According to Profile

a. Tech-Voc School Teachers

a.1 Personal Competencies and Persistence

Table 12. Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Level of Resilience of the Tech-Voc School Teachers in Terms of Personal Competencies and Persistence When Grouped According to Their Profile

Level of Resilience in Terms of Personal Competencies and Persistence and the Following Profile	Probability of F	Decision	Remarks
Age	0.00000019	Reject H ₀	Significant
Sex	0.00010052	Reject H ₀	Significant
Civil Status	0.00005860	Reject H ₀	Significant
Educational Attainment	0.00000000	Reject H ₀	Significant
Teaching Position	0.00000000	Reject H ₀	Significant
Length of Service	0.00000018	Reject H ₀	Significant

Table 12 presents the results of the test of significant difference in the level of resilience of the Tech-Voc School teachers in terms of personal competencies and persistence when grouped according to their profile.

The results show that the F-probability values are less than 0.05, hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at a 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is a significant difference in the level of resilience of the Tech-Voc School teachers in terms of personal competencies and persistence when grouped according to their profile. It implies that the Tech-Voc School teachers' resilience in terms of personal competence and persistence differ when grouped by age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, teaching position, and length of service. It is further inferred as indicated by the mean in Appendix C that those Tech-Voc School teachers who are 41-45 years old, with doctorate units and a doctorate holder, master teacher 2, and have been in the service for 16-20 years have *very high* resilience in their competencies and persistence, and those who are male and married have *high* resilience along this area.

As regards their *age*, there exists significant difference, but each age group is still within the same level of high resilience contrary to the findings of Amin et al (2022). which found out that the older a staff member is, the less resilient he/she is. Moreover, Sarmiento, Ponce, and Bertolín (2021) revealed that students over 25 years, for almost all factors, and males, with a not very significant difference from female students, had higher scores on the construct of resilience. Labrague and Ballad (2020) explored a study on resilience that reveals sex-related differences. Roman-Mata et. al (2020). found out that employed people, those with higher education, presented higher rates of resilience.

a.2 Family Cohesion

Table 13. Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Level of Resilience of the Tech-Voc School Teachers in Terms of Family Cohesion When Grouped According to Their Profile

Level of Resilience in Terms of Family Cohesion and the Following Profile	Probability of F	Decision	Remarks
Age	0.00000056	Reject H ₀	Significant
Sex	0.00041262	Reject H ₀	Significant
Civil Status	0.00005955	Reject H ₀	Significant
Educational Attainment	0.00000000	Reject H ₀	Significant
Teaching Position	0.00000000	Reject H ₀	Significant
Length of Service	0.00000057	Reject H ₀	Significant

The results of the test of significant difference in the level of resilience of the Tech-Voc school teachers in terms of family cohesion, when grouped according to their profile, are presented in Table 13.

It is revealed from the results that the probability values of F are less than 0.05. This signifies the rejection of the null hypothesis at a 0.05 significance level. Therefore, there is a significant difference in the level of resilience of the Tech-Voc School teachers in terms of family cohesion when grouped according to their profile. This means that the Tech-Voc School teachers have different level of resilience along family cohesion when they are classified by age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, teaching position, and length of service. As appended, it is noted that the Tech-Voc School teachers who belong to the 51-60 age bracket, are female, married, doctorate holders, master teacher 2, and with work experience for 26-30 years, have *very high* resilience in terms of family cohesion.

It is notable that with regard to their sex, female teachers from Tech-Voc School possess a higher level of resilience than males, though overall, both groups of male and female respondents are described as having very high resilience levels. Such findings relate to that of Amin et al (2022). which found out that based on gender, the level of resilience for both male and female lecturers is within the same level of high resilience, with females having a slightly higher rate than males. Furthermore, the findings that women are more resilient than men are consistent with the study of Sun and Stewart (2007). Although the subjects in that study were children and adolescents. Relatively, Roman-Mata et al. (2020) found that those with dependents presented higher rates of resilience.

a.3 Social Skills and Peer Support

Table 14. Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Level of Resilience of the Tech-Voc School Teachers in Terms of Social Skills and Peer Support When Grouped According to Their Profile

Level of Resilience in Terms of Social Skills and Peer Support and the Following Profile	Probability of F	Decision	Remarks
Age	0.00000028	Reject H ₀	Significant
Sex	0.00187000	Reject H ₀	Significant
Civil Status	0.00005750	Reject H ₀	Significant
Educational Attainment	0.00000000	Reject H ₀	Significant
Teaching Position	0.00000000	Reject H ₀	Significant
Length of Service	0.00000028	Reject H ₀	Significant

Table 14 reveals the results of the test of significant difference in the level of resilience of the Tech-Voc school teachers in terms of social skills and peer support when grouped according to their profile.

The results reflect that the F-probability values are less than 0.05. For this reason, the null hypothesis is rejected at a 0.05 level of significance. As a result, there is a significant difference in the level of resilience of the Tech-Voc school teachers in terms of social skills and peer support when grouped according to their profile. It shows that the teachers vary from each other in their resilience level along with social skills and peer support when clustered by their age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, teaching position, and length of service. It further infers, as indicated by the mean in Appendix C, that those teachers who are of age 41-45, female, married, with doctorate units and a doctorate holder, master teachers 1, and have been in the service for 16-20 years, have *very high* resilience.

With respect to the *length of service*, the present study found a significant difference, but respondents are within the same level of high resilience opposing to Amin et al.'s (2022) findings that length of tenure negatively correlates with the level of resilience in the tenure group of 1-6 years, 7-21 years, and 21 years and above, although on average all groups are still categorized as having high resilience. Freedman & Appleman (2008) asserted that peer factors are significant in building teachers' resilience, especially at the early stages of careers. A study by Liang et al.(2020) affirmed that supportive coworkers in the workplace should be demonstrated to sustain resilience among educators.

a.4 Spiritual Influences

Table 15. Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Level of Resilience of the Tech-Voc School Teachers in Terms of Spiritual Influences When Grouped According to Their Profile

Level of Resilience in Terms of Spiritual Influences and the Following Profile	Probability of F	Decision	Remarks
Age	0.0000006 4	Reject H ₀	Significant
Sex	0.0035201 4	Reject H ₀	Significant
Civil Status	0.0000226 8	Reject H ₀	Significant
Educational Attainment	0.0000000 0	Reject H ₀	Significant
Teaching Position	0.0000000 0	Reject H ₀	Significant
Length of Service	0.0000005 4	Reject H ₀	Significant

The results of the test of significant difference in the level of resilience of the Tech-Voc school teachers in terms of spiritual influences, when grouped according to their profile, are displayed in Table 15.

It is evident from the results that the P-values of F are less than 0.05, hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at a 0.05 significance level. Thus, there is a significant difference in the level of resilience of the Tech-Voc school teachers in terms of spiritual influences when grouped according to their profile. It implies that the teachers' resilience differs from each other along spiritual influences when grouped by their age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, teaching position, and length of service. As appended, the spiritual influence is *very high* among the teachers who are of age 46-50, female, married, with doctorate units, teacher 3 and have been working for 16-20 years.

A study by Malcom (2007) disclosed that adults had a sense of faith and considered themselves to be religious or spiritual.

b. Non-Tech-Voc School Teachers

b.1 Personal Competencies and Persistence

Table 16. Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Level of Resilience of the Non-Tech-Voc School Teachers in Terms of Personal Competencies and Persistence When Grouped According to Their Profile

Level of Resilience in Terms of Personal Competencies and Persistence and the Following Profile	Probability of F	Decision	Remarks
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Age	0.0000000 0	Reject H ₀	Significant
Sex	0.0005310 0	Reject H ₀	Significant
Civil Status	0.0000062 4	Reject H ₀	Significant
Educational Attainment	0.0000000 0	Reject H ₀	Significant
Teaching Position	0.0000000 0	Reject H ₀	Significant
Length of Service	0.0000000 1	Reject H ₀	Significant

Table 16 discloses the results of the test of significant difference in the level of resilience of the Non-Tech-Voc School teachers in terms of personal competencies and persistence when grouped according to their profile.

The results reveal that the F-probability values are less than 0.05. This signifies the rejection of the null hypothesis at a 0.05 significance level. Therefore, there is a significant difference in the level of resilience of the Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers in terms of personal competencies and persistence when grouped according to their profile. It shows that the Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers have different resilience levels along the said category when classified by age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, teaching position, and length of service. As indicated by the mean in Appendix C, the personal competencies and persistence are *very high* among the teachers who are of age 36-40, doctorate holders and have been in the service for 16-20 years. Whereas the said resilience is *high* among the teachers who are male, single, and with Teacher 1 position.

As noted, Non-Tech-Voc School male teachers have a higher level of resilience than females. Such a finding is consistent with that of Erdogan et al.'s (2015) findings that males are more resilient than females. Overall, both groups of male and female respondents are described as having very high in their resilience levels. Relatively, Polat and Iskender (2018) did not find any significant difference in the resilience of male and female teachers. Roman-Mata et. al (2020). found out that employed people, those with higher education, presented higher rates of resilience.

b.2 Family Cohesion

Table 17. Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Level of Resilience of the Non-Tech-Voc High School Teachers in Terms of Family Cohesion When Grouped According to Their Profile

Level of Resilience in Terms of Family Cohesion and the Following Profile	Probability of F	Decision	Remarks
Age	0.0000000 0	Reject H ₀	Significant

Sex	0.0000260 0	Reject H ₀	Significant
Civil Status	0.0000017 3	Reject H ₀	Significant
Educational Attainment	0.0000000 0	Reject H ₀	Significant
Teaching Position	0.0000000 0	Reject H ₀	Significant
Length of Service	0.0000000 3	Reject H ₀	Significant

The results of the test of significant difference in the level of resilience of the Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers in terms of family cohesion, when grouped according to their profile, are disclosed in Table 17.

It is revealed from the results that the P-values of F are less than 0.05. For this reason, the null hypothesis is rejected at a 0.05 level of significance. As a result, there is a significant difference in the level of resilience of the Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers in terms of family cohesion when grouped according to their profile. It implies that the teachers vary from each other in their resilience level along family cohesion when clustered by age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, teaching position, and length of service. In this study, it is noted that family cohesion is *very high* among the teachers who are of age 41-45, female, married, doctorate holders, master teachers 1, and worked for 16-20 years.

Noticeably, with regard to their *age*, there exists significant difference, but each age group is still within the same level of high resilience contrary to the findings of Amin et al. (2022) which found that the older a staff member is, the less resilient he/she is. Relatively, Roman-Mata et al.(2020) found that those with dependents presented higher rates of resilience.

b.3 Social Skills and Peer Support

Table 18. Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Level of Resilience of the Non-Tech-Voc High School Teachers in Terms of Social Skills and Peer Support When Grouped According to Their Profile

Level of Resilience in Terms of Social Skills and Peer Support and the Following Profile	Probability of F	Decision	Remarks
Age	0.0000000 0	Reject H ₀	Significant
Sex	0.0001260 0	Reject H ₀	Significant
Civil Status	0.0000004 1	Reject H ₀	Significant
Educational Attainment	0.0000000 0	Reject H ₀	Significant

Teaching Position	0.0000000 0	Reject H ₀	Significant
Length of Service	0.0000000 1	Reject H ₀	Significant

Table 18 exhibits the results of the test of significant difference in the level of resilience of the Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers in terms of social skills and peer support when grouped according to their profile.

The results show that the F-probability values are less than 0.05, hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at a 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is a significant difference in the level of resilience of the Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers in terms of social skills and peer support when grouped according to their profile. Teachers differ in their resilience level along social skills and peer support when grouped by age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, teaching position, and length of service. As evidenced by the mean in Appendix C, the teachers aged 46-50, female, widowed, doctorate holders, master teachers 2, and served for 21-25 years, have *very high* resilience along the said indicator.

Regarding the *length of service*, the present study found a significant difference, but respondents are within the same level of high resilience negating that of Amin et al.(2022) findings that length of tenure negatively correlates with the level of resilience in the tenure group of 1-6 years, 7-21 years, and 21 years and above, although on average all groups are still categorized as having high resilience. Freedman & Appleman (2008) affirm that peer factors are significant in building teachers' resilience, especially at the early stages of careers. Teachers get optimism and aspiration from their coworkers in any challenging situation as reported by Anderson and Olsen (2006).

b.4 Spiritual Influences

Table 19. Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Level of Resilience of the Non-Tech-Voc School Teachers in Terms of Spiritual Influences When Grouped According to Their Profile

Level of Resilience in Terms of Spiritual Influences and the Following Profile	Probability of F	Decision	Remarks
Age	0.0000000 0	Reject H ₀	Significant
Sex	0.0004280 0	Reject H ₀	Significant
Civil Status	0.0000070 1	Reject H ₀	Significant
Educational Attainment	0.0000000 0	Reject H ₀	Significant
Teaching Position	0.0000000 0	Reject H ₀	Significant
Length of Service	0.0000000 3	Reject H ₀	Significant

The results of the test of significant difference in the level of resilience of the Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers in terms of spiritual influences, when grouped according to their profile, are exhibited in Table 19.

It is evident from the results that the P-values of F are less than 0.05. This signifies the rejection of the null hypothesis at a 0.05 significance level. Therefore, there is a significant difference in the level of resilience of the Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers in terms of spiritual influences when grouped according to their profile. It shows that the teachers have different resilience level along spiritual influences when classified by age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, teaching position, and length of service. As appended, the spiritual influence is *very high* among the teachers who are of age 36-40, male, single, bachelor's and master's degree holders, teachers 2, and have worked for 6-10 years.

Malcom (2007) revealed in a study that adults had a sense of faith and considered themselves to be religious or spiritual.

4. Significant Difference Between Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc School Teachers' Level of Resilience

Table 20. Results of the Test of Significant Difference Between Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc School Teachers' Level of Resilience

Resilience	Mean		Probability of t	Decision	Remarks
	Tech-Voc School Teachers	Non-Tech-Voc High School Teachers			
Personal Competencies and Persistence	4.02	4.13	0.02434	Reject H ₀	Significant
Family Cohesion	4.59	4.58	0.71410	Accept H ₀	Not Significant
Social Skills and Peer Support	4.21	4.21	0.93900	Accept H ₀	Not Significant
Spiritual Influences	4.69	4.69	0.90220	Accept H ₀	Not Significant

Table 20 discloses the results of the test of significant difference between Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc School teachers' level of resilience

The results show that the probability value of t for personal competencies and persistence is less than 0.05, hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at a 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is a significant difference between Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers' level of resilience in terms of personal competencies and persistence. It implies that the resilience of the Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers in this area differs from that of the Tech-Voc school teachers. It further states as indicated by the mean in the table that the Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers have *higher*

resilience in terms of personal competencies and persistence than the Tech-Voc teachers.

However, there is no significant difference between the Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers' level of resilience in family cohesion, social skills and peer support, and spiritual influences. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted at a 0.05 significance level. It indicates that the two groups of teachers have similarities in their resilience levels along these three domains. Relative to this, Gu and Day (2007) specified that personal characteristics, competencies, and positive influences of the social environment in which the individual works and lives, independently and together interact to contribute to the process of resilience building.

5. Respondents' Level of Work Performance

a. Task Performance

Table 21. Respondents' Level of Work Performance in Terms of Task Performance

Task Performance	Tech-Voc School Teachers		Non-Tech-Voc School Teachers	
	Weighted Mean	Description	Weighted Mean	Description
1. I manage to plan my work so that it is done on time.	4.45	Outstanding	4.48	Outstanding
2. My planning is optimal.	4.14	Very Satisfactory	4.09	Very Satisfactory
3. I keep in mind the results that I have to achieve in my work.	4.53	Outstanding	4.54	Outstanding
4. I am able to separate main issues from side issues at work.	4.45	Outstanding	4.45	Outstanding
5. I know how to set the right priorities.	4.39	Outstanding	4.65	Outstanding
6. I am able to perform my work well with minimal time and effort.	4.20	Outstanding	4.18	Very Satisfactory
7. Collaboration with others is very productive.	4.63	Outstanding	4.56	Outstanding
Category Mean	4.40	Outstanding	4.42	Outstanding

Table 21 exhibits the respondents' work performance level in terms of task performance. Both Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers generally say "their planning is optimal" with a mean of 4.14 and 4.09 respectively, described as *very satisfactory*. Furthermore, Tech-Voc School teachers *always* while Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers *often* are "able to perform their work well with minimal time and effort" with 4.20 and 4.18 interpreted as *outstanding* and *very satisfactory* correspondingly. Both groups got an *outstanding* performance in all the other items in which "they manage to plan their work so that it is done on time; keep in mind the results that they have to achieve in their work; separate main issues from side issues at work; know how to set the right priorities; and collaboration with others is very productive."

As indicated, both Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers attained a mean of 4.40 and 4.42 respectively, which indicate that they possess an *outstanding* task performance. This means that the primary role of teachers inside the classroom is excellently done.

Undoubtedly, teachers do their primary job as classroom teachers. Passion and dedication to teaching are unequivocally manifested by them during the new normal, guided by the mission and vision of the department. School heads are encouraged to always appreciate the teachers for them to be inspired and motivated always.

In a study by Mbon (2017), it is revealed that head teachers' decision-making strategy and leadership style have a significant influence on teachers' task performance. Also, head teachers' communication skills significantly relate to teachers' task performance. He concluded that proper managerial behavior boosts teachers' morale towards high task performance.

b. Contextual Performance

Table 22. Respondents' Level of Work Performance In terms of Contextual Performance

Contextual Performance	Tech-Voc School Teachers		National High (Non-Tech-Voc) School Teachers	
	Weighted Mean	Description	Weighted Mean	Description
1. I take on extra responsibilities.	4.49	Outstanding	4.35	Outstanding
2. I start new tasks myself when my old ones are finished.	4.25	Outstanding	4.22	Outstanding
3. I take on challenging work tasks when available.	4.27	Outstanding	4.23	Outstanding
4. I work at keeping my job knowledge up-to-date.	4.27	Outstanding	4.44	Outstanding
5. I work at keeping my job skills up-to-date.	4.42	Outstanding	4.44	Outstanding
6. I come up with creative solutions to new problems.	4.19	Very Satisfactory	4.20	Outstanding
7. I keep looking for new challenges in my job.	4.08	Very Satisfactory	4.05	Very Satisfactory
8. I do more than what is expected of me.	4.32	Outstanding	4.29	Outstanding
9. I actively participate in work meetings.	4.31	Outstanding	4.36	Outstanding
10. I actively look for ways to improve my performance at work.	4.45	Outstanding	4.53	Outstanding
11. I grasp opportunities when they present themselves.	4.35	Outstanding	4.36	Outstanding

12. I know how to solve difficult situations and setbacks quickly.	4.12	Very Satisfactory	4.07	Very Satisfactory
Category Mean	4.29	Outstanding	4.30	Outstanding

Table 22 discloses the respondents' work performance level relative to contextual performance. Both Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers say "they keep looking for new challenges in their job" with a mean of 4.08 and 4.05 respectively, described as *very satisfactory*. Likewise, both Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers rated themselves *very satisfactory* in "knowing how to solve difficult situations and setbacks quickly." On the other hand, Tech-Voc School teachers perform *very satisfactorily* while Non-Tech-Voc School teachers are *outstanding* in "coming up with creative solutions to new problems" with 4.19 and 4.20 correspondingly. Both groups got *outstanding* performances in "taking on extra responsibilities, and actively looking for ways to improve their performance at work."

As shown, both Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers got a mean of 4.29 and 4.30 respectively, which implies that they have an *outstanding* contextual performance which is the extra responsibilities done by teachers aside from teaching.

This indicates that apart from doing their primary duties and responsibilities in the classroom, teachers also willingly do extra-curricular activities in their respective schools like having coordinators in their subjects and curriculum, mentoring and coaching their students and their colleagues as needed, keeping their knowledge and skills up-to-date by attending trainings and seminars, actively participate in work meetings, and other extra-roles. These were confirmed by the respondents during informal dialogues. Relative to this, Nini (2019) affirmed that contextual performance is activities like coaching colleagues, strengthening social networks in an organization, and increasing the organization's workflow.

c. Work Behavior

Table 23. Respondents' Level of Work Performance in Terms of Work Behavior

Work Behavior	Tech-Voc School Teachers		Non-Tech-Voc School Teachers	
	Weighted Mean	Description	Weighted Mean	Description
1. I complain about unimportant matters at work.	2.07	Rarely	2.10	Rarely
2. I make problems greater than they were at work.	1.52	Never	1.58	Never
3. I focus on the negative aspects of a work situation, instead of on the positive aspects.	1.47	Never	1.43	Never
4. I speak with colleagues about the negative aspects of my work.	1.81	Rarely	1.59	Never

5. I speak with people from outside the organization about the negative aspects of my work.	1.52	Never	1.34	Never
6. I do less than is expected of me.	1.45	Never	1.44	Never
7. I manage to get off from a work task easily.	1.66	Never	1.75	Never
8. I do nothing, while I should have been working.	1.36	Never	1.35	Never
Category Mean	1.61	Outstanding	1.57	Outstanding

Table 23 denotes the respondents' work performance level in terms of work behavior. Both Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers just *rarely* "complain about unimportant matters at work" with a mean of 2.07 and 2.10 respectively, interpreted as *very satisfactory*. On the other hand, Tech-Voc School teachers *rarely* while Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers *never* "speak with colleagues about the negative aspects of their work" with 1.81 and 1.59, inferred as *very satisfactory* and *outstanding* correspondingly. Both groups got *outstanding* performance in all the other items where they *never* "do nothing, while they should have been working" (1.36, 1.35) and *never* "speak with people from outside the organization about the negative aspects of their work" (1.52, 1.34) respectively.

Both Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers attained a category mean of 1.61 and 1.57 respectively, which indicates that they have an *outstanding* work behavior that pertains to the teachers' behavior in the performance of their duties and responsibilities.

Guided by their oath and code of ethics in their profession, teachers possess good attitudes and behavior in their workplace, especially during or in the new normal. They affirm that they religiously do their work performance with loyalty. Ramdani, Marliani, and Rahman (2019) emphasized that employees' work behavior is directly related to the productivity that will result from their work.

d. IPCRF Key Result Areas

d.1 KRA 1 - Content Knowledge and Pedagogy

Table 24. Respondents' Level of Work Performance in Terms of IPCRF Key Result Area 1

KRA 1 - Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	Tech-Voc School Teachers		Non-Tech-Voc School Teachers	
	Weighted Mean	Description	Weighted Mean	Description
<i>Teacher 1-3</i>				
1. I apply knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas.	4.69	Outstanding	4.67	Outstanding

2. I use research-based knowledge and principles of teaching and learning to enhance professional practice.	4.30	Outstanding	4.47	Outstanding
3. I display proficient use of Mother Tongue, Filipino, and English to facilitate teaching and learning.	4.65	Outstanding	4.70	Outstanding
4. I use verbal and non-verbal classroom communication strategies to support learner understanding, participation, engagement, and achievement.	4.74	Outstanding	4.74	Outstanding
Category Mean	4.60	Outstanding	4.65	Outstanding
<i>Master Teacher 1-2</i>				
1. I model effective applications of content knowledge within and across curriculum teaching areas.	4.57	Outstanding	4.44	Outstanding
2. I evaluate with colleagues the effectiveness of teaching strategies that promote learner achievement in literacy and numeracy.	4.00	Very Satisfactory	3.69	Very Satisfactory
3. I model and support colleagues in the proficient use of Mother Tongue, Filipino and English to improve teaching and learning, as well as to develop learners' pride of their language, heritage, and culture.	4.57	Outstanding	4.38	Outstanding
4. I display a wide range of effective verbal and non-verbal classroom communication strategies to support learner understanding, participation, engagement, and achievement.	4.71	Outstanding	4.50	Outstanding
Category Mean	4.46	Outstanding	4.25	Outstanding

Table 24 denotes the respondents' work performance level in terms of IPCRF KRA 1 - Content Knowledge and Pedagogy. As manifested, teachers 1-3 from Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc High Schools acquired a category mean of 4.60 and 4.65 respectively, which means that they have an *outstanding* performance in Content Knowledge and Pedagogy.

Teachers 1-3 from Tech-Voc School got weighted mean values ranging from 4.30 to 4.74 while the Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers garnered weighted mean

responses ranging from 4.47 to 4.74 which means that all the items in KRA 1 are demonstrated by both groups of respondents to an *outstanding* level.

Meanwhile, master teachers 1-2 from both Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc High Schools self-rated themselves *very satisfactory* in the item “evaluate with colleagues the effectiveness of teaching strategies that promote learner achievement in literacy and numeracy” with a mean of 4.00 and 3.69, respectively. All the other items are rated *outstanding*.

Master teachers 1-2 from Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc High Schools got a category mean of 4.46 and 4.25 respectively, which infers that in this KRA, they possess an *outstanding* performance.

In conclusion, both groups of teachers 1-3 and master teachers 1-2 from Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc High Schools manifest an *outstanding* performance in KRA 1 - Content Knowledge and Pedagogy.

As surfaced during the informal conversation, teachers see to it that during classroom instructions, they apply knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas. They connect their lessons to other learning areas so that meaningful learning is achieved by the learners.

d.2 KRA 2 - Learning Environment

Table 25. Respondents’ Level of Work Performance in Terms of IPCRF Key Result Area 2

KRA 2 - Learning Environment	Tech-Voc School Teachers		Non-Tech-Voc School Teachers	
	Weighted Mean	Description	Weighted Mean	Description
<i>Teacher 1-3</i>				
1. I establish safe and secure learning environments to enhance learning through the consistent implementation of policies, guidelines, and procedures.	4.78	Outstanding	4.75	Outstanding
2. I maintain learning environments that promote fairness, respect, and care to encourage learning.	4.83	Outstanding	4.80	Outstanding
3. I maintain learning environments to nurture and inspire learners to participate, cooperate and collaborate in continued learning.	4.87	Outstanding	4.70	Outstanding

4. I apply range of successful strategies that maintain learning environments that motivate learners to work productively by assuming responsibility for their own learning.	4.77	Outstanding	4.71	Outstanding
Category Mean	4.81	Outstanding	4.74	Outstanding
<i>Master Teacher 1-2</i>				
1. I exhibit effective strategies that ensure safe and secure learning environments to enhance learning through the consistent implementation of policies, guidelines, and procedures.	4.86	Outstanding	4.38	Outstanding
2. I exhibit effective practices to foster learning environments that promote fairness, respect, and care to encourage learning.	4.86	Outstanding	4.44	Outstanding
3. I work with colleagues to share successful strategies that sustain supportive learning environments that nurture and inspire learners to participate, cooperate and collaborate in continued learning.	4.86	Outstanding	4.44	Outstanding
4. I model successful strategies and support colleagues in promoting learning environments that effectively motivate learners to work productively by assuming responsibility for their own learning.	4.71	Outstanding	4.44	Outstanding
Category Mean	4.82	Outstanding	4.43	Outstanding

Table 25 unveils the respondents' work performance level in terms of IPCRF KRA 2 - Learning Environment. As shown, teachers 1-3 from Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc High Schools acquired a category mean of 4.81 and 4.74 respectively, which indicates that in this domain, they possess an *outstanding* performance.

Teachers 1-3 from Tech-Voc School got weighted mean values ranging from 4.77 to 4.87 while the Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers garnered weighted mean responses ranging from 4.70 to 4.80 which means that all the items in KRA 2 are demonstrated by both groups of respondents to an *outstanding* level.

Meanwhile, master teachers 1-2 from Tech-Voc School got weighted mean values ranging from 4.71 to 4.86 whereas the Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers garnered weighted mean responses ranging from 4.38 to 4.44 which means that all the items in KRA 2 are manifested by both groups of respondents to an *outstanding* level.

Master teachers 1-2 from Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc High Schools got a category mean of 4.82 and 4.43 respectively, which infers that in this KRA, they possess an *outstanding* performance.

In conclusion, both groups of teachers 1-3 and master teachers 1-2 from Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc High Schools demonstrate an *outstanding* performance in KRA 2 - Learning Environment.

Teachers are said to have established and exhibited effective strategies that ensure safe and secure learning environments, promoting fairness, respect, and care to encourage learning. These were affirmed during dialogue with the respondents.

d.3 KRA 3 - Diversity of Learners, Curriculum and Planning, and Assessment and Reporting

Table 26. Respondents' Level of Work Performance in Terms of IPCRF Key Result Area 3

KRA 3 - Diversity of Learners, Curriculum and Planning, and Assessment and Reporting	Tech-Voc School Teachers		Non-Tech-Voc School Teachers	
	Weighted Mean	Description	Weighted Mean	Description
<i>Teacher 1-3</i>				
1. I design, adapt, and implement teaching strategies that are responsive to learners with disabilities, giftedness, and talents.	4.56	Outstanding	4.65	Outstanding
2. I adapt and use culturally appropriate teaching strategies to address the needs of learners from indigenous groups.	4.58	Outstanding	4.60	Outstanding
3. I adapt and implement learning programs that ensure relevance and responsiveness to the needs of all learners.	4.65	Outstanding	4.67	Outstanding
4. I utilize assessment data to inform the modification of teaching and learning practices and programs.	4.68	Outstanding	4.68	Outstanding
Category Mean	4.62	Outstanding	4.65	Outstanding
<i>Master Teacher 1-2</i>				
1. I assist colleagues to design, adapt and implement teaching strategies that are responsive to learners with disabilities, giftedness, and talents.	4.57	Outstanding	4.19	Outstanding

2. I develop and apply teaching strategies to address effectively the needs of learners from indigenous groups.	4.57	Outstanding	4.38	Outstanding
3. I work collaboratively with colleagues to evaluate the design of learning programs that develop the knowledge and skills of learners at different ability levels.	4.71	Outstanding	4.31	Outstanding
4. I work collaboratively with colleagues to analyze and utilize assessment data to modify practices and programs to further support learner progress and achievement.	4.57	Outstanding	4.38	Outstanding
Category Mean	4.61	Outstanding	4.32	Outstanding

Table 26 reveals the respondents' work performance level in terms of IPCRF KRA 3 - Diversity of Learners, Curriculum and Planning, and Assessment and Reporting. As presented, teachers 1-3 from Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc High Schools acquired a category mean of 4.62 and 4.65 respectively, which imply that in this domain, they possess an *outstanding* performance.

Teachers 1-3 from both Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc High Schools rated themselves *outstanding* in all the items with weighted mean values ranging from 4.56 to 4.68 and 4.60 to 4.68 respectively, which mean that all the items in KRA 3 are demonstrated by both group of respondents to an *outstanding* level. They assert that they “design, adapt, and implement teaching strategies that are responsive to learners with disabilities, giftedness, and talents; and utilize assessment data to inform the modification of teaching and learning practices and programs.”

Meanwhile, master teachers 1-2 from Tech-Voc School got weighted mean values ranging from 4.57 to 4.71 whereas the Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers garnered weighted mean responses ranging from 4.19 to 4.38 which means that all the items in KRA 3 are manifested by both groups of respondents to an *outstanding* level.

Master teachers 1-2 from Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc High Schools got a category mean of 4.61 and 4.32 respectively, which infers that in this KRA, they possess an *outstanding* performance. They assert “develop and apply teaching strategies to address effectively the needs of learners from indigenous groups, and work collaboratively with colleagues to evaluate the design of learning programs that develop the knowledge and skills of learners at different ability levels.”

In conclusion, both groups of teachers 1-3 and master teachers 1-2 from Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc High Schools demonstrate *outstanding* performance in KRA 3 - Diversity of Learners, Curriculum and Planning, and Assessment and Reporting.

Teachers confirm that they do planning, designing, adapting, and implementing teaching strategies to address the needs of learners. They also do regular assessments and reporting for the students to know how far they have gone as to the learning competencies they have to acquire.

d.4 KRA 4 - Community Linkages and Professional Engagement and Personal Growth and Professional Development

Table 27. Respondents' Level of Work Performance in Terms of IPCRF Key Result Area 4

KRA 4 - Community Linkages and Professional Engagement and Personal Growth and Professional Development	Tech-Voc School Teachers		Non-Tech-Voc School Teachers	
	Weighted Mean	Description	Weighted Mean	Description
<i>Teacher 1-3</i>				
1. I maintain learning environments that are responsive to community contexts.	4.73	Outstanding	4.75	Outstanding
2. I review regularly personal teaching practice using existing laws and regulations that apply to the teaching profession and the responsibilities specified in the Code of Ethics for Professional Teachers.	4.62	Outstanding	4.70	Outstanding
3. I comply with implemented school policies and procedures consistently to foster harmonious relationships with learners, parents, and other stakeholders.	4.80	Outstanding	4.77	Outstanding
4. I apply personal philosophy of teaching that is learner-centered.	4.79	Outstanding	4.78	Outstanding
5. I adopt practices that uphold the dignity of teaching as a profession by exhibiting qualities such as caring attitude, respect, and integrity.	4.78	Outstanding	4.79	Outstanding
6. I set professional development goals based on the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers.	4.78	Outstanding	4.73	Outstanding
Category Mean	4.75	Outstanding	4.75	Outstanding
<i>Master Teacher 1-2</i>				
1. I reflect on and evaluate learning environments that are responsive to community contexts.	4.71	Outstanding	4.38	Outstanding

2. I discuss with colleagues teaching and learning practices that apply existing codes, laws and regulations that apply to the teaching profession, and the responsibilities specified in the <i>Code of Ethics for Professional Teachers</i> .	4.71	Outstanding	4.38	Outstanding
3. I exhibit commitment to and support teachers in the implementation of school policies and procedures to foster harmonious relationships with learners, parents, and other stakeholders.	4.86	Outstanding	4.50	Outstanding
4. I manifest a learner-centered teaching philosophy in various aspects of practice and support colleagues in enhancing their own learner centered teaching philosophy.	4.86	Outstanding	4.50	Outstanding
5. I identify and utilize personal professional strengths to uphold the dignity of teaching as a profession to help build a positive teaching and learning culture within the school.	4.86	Outstanding	4.63	Outstanding
6. I reflect on the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers to plan personal professional development goals and assist colleagues in planning and achieving their own goals.	4.86	Outstanding	4.81	Outstanding
Category Mean	4.81	Outstanding	4.53	Outstanding

Table 27 reveals the respondents' work performance level in terms of IPCRF KRA 4 - Community Linkages and Professional Engagement and Personal Growth and Professional Development. As shown in the table, teachers 1-3 from both Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc High Schools attained a category mean of 4.75, which imply that in this domain, they possess an *outstanding* performance.

Teachers 1-3 from both Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc High Schools rated themselves *outstanding* in all the items with weighted mean values ranging from 4.62 to 4.80 and 4.70 to 4.79 respectively, which infer that all the items in KRA 4 are demonstrated by both group of respondents to an *outstanding* level. They confirm that they "review regularly personal teaching practice using existing laws and regulations that apply to the teaching profession and the responsibilities specified in the Code of Ethics for Professional Teachers; and comply with implemented school policies and procedures

consistently to foster harmonious relationships with learners, parents, and other stakeholders.”

Moreover, master teachers 1-2 from Tech-Voc School got weighted mean values ranging from 4.71 to 4.86 whereas the Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers garnered weighted mean responses ranging from 4.38 to 4.81 which describe that all the items in KRA 4 are manifested by both group of respondents to an *outstanding* level.

Master teachers 1-2 from Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc High Schools got a category mean of 4.81 and 4.53 respectively, which infer that in this KRA, they possess an *outstanding* performance. They affirm that they “reflect on and evaluate learning environments that are responsive to community contexts; and reflect on the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers to plan personal professional development goals and assist colleagues in planning and achieving their own goals.”

In conclusion, both groups of teachers 1-3 and master teachers 1-2 from Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc High Schools demonstrate *outstanding* performance in KRA 4 - Community Linkages and Professional Engagement and Personal Growth and Professional Development.

Teachers affirm that they keep a learning environment that is responsive to community context. Also, they consistently observe the implemented school policies and procedures to foster harmonious relationships with learners, parents, and other stakeholders. They set professional development goals based on the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers by attending graduate studies, trainings, and seminars to enrich their knowledge.

d.5 KRA 5 – Plus Factor

Table 28. Respondents’ Level of Work Performance in Terms of IPCRF Key Result Area 5

KRA 5 - Plus Factor	Tech-Voc School Teachers		Non-Tech-Voc School Teachers	
	Weighted Mean	Description	Weighted Mean	Description
<i>Teacher 1-3</i>				
I do perform various related works/activities that contribute to the teaching-learning process.	4.80	Outstanding	4.81	Outstanding
Category Mean	4.80	Outstanding	4.81	Outstanding
<i>Master Teacher 1-2</i>				
I do perform various related works/activities that contribute to the teaching-learning process.	4.86	Outstanding	4.56	Outstanding
Category Mean	4.86	Outstanding	4.56	Outstanding

Table 28 reveals the respondents' work performance level in terms of the IPCRF KRA 5 – Plus Factor. As gleaned in the table, teachers 1-3 from Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc High Schools attained a weighted and category mean of 4.80 and 4.81 correspondingly, which infer that in this domain, they possess an *outstanding* performance.

Likewise, master teachers 1-2 from Tech-Voc School got a weighted and category mean of 4.86 whereas the Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers garnered 4.56 which describes that KRA 5 is manifested by both groups of respondents to an *outstanding* level.

In conclusion, both groups of teachers 1-3 and master teachers 1-2 from Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc High Schools demonstrate an *outstanding* performance in KRA 5 - Plus Factor. In this KRA, teachers perform other tasks aside from teaching.

In an informal interview, teachers confirm that they perform different related works/activities that contribute to the teaching-learning process. They mentor and coach students for their co-curricular and extra-curricular activities, mentoring of pre-service teachers, have coordinatorships, chairmanship, pursue post-graduate studies, and others.

Table 29. Summary of the Respondents' IPCRF Key Result Areas

IPCRF Key Result Areas	Tech-Voc School Teachers		Non-Tech-Voc School Teachers	
	Weighted Mean	Description	Weighted Mean	Description
<i>T1 to T3</i>				
KRA 1	4.60	Outstanding	4.65	Outstanding
KRA 2	4.81	Outstanding	4.74	Outstanding
KRA 3	4.62	Outstanding	4.65	Outstanding
KRA 4	4.75	Outstanding	4.75	Outstanding
KRA 5	4.80	Outstanding	4.81	Outstanding
Mean	4.72	Outstanding	4.72	Outstanding
<i>MT1 to MT2</i>				
KRA 1	4.46	Outstanding	4.25	Outstanding
KRA 2	4.82	Outstanding	4.43	Outstanding
KRA 3	4.61	Outstanding	4.32	Outstanding
KRA 4	4.81	Outstanding	4.53	Outstanding
KRA 5	4.86	Outstanding	4.56	Outstanding
Mean	4.71	Outstanding	4.42	Outstanding
IPCRF KRA Overall Mean	4.72	Outstanding	4.57	Outstanding

The summary of the respondents' IPCRF Key Result Areas is presented in Table 29. It is revealed that Teachers 1 to 3 from both Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc Schools got an *outstanding* performance along all the KRAs with weighted means ranging from 4.60 to 4.81 and 4.65 to 4.81, respectively. Meanwhile, Master Teachers 1 to 2 from both

Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc Schools also possess an *outstanding* performance in all KRAs with weighted means ranging from 4.46 to 4.86 and 4.25 to 4.56, respectively.

This implies that teachers do multitasking. As they affirm, aside from doing their primary roles as classroom teachers, they also do related works and activities that could greatly contribute to organizational effectiveness, productivity, and success.

Table 30. Summary of the Respondents' Level of Work Performance

Work Performance	Tech-Voc School Teachers		Non-Tech-Voc School Teachers	
	Weighted Mean	Description	Weighted Mean	Description
a. Task Performance	4.40	Outstanding	4.42	Outstanding
b. Contextual Performance	4.29	Outstanding	4.30	Outstanding
c. IPCRF KRA	4.72	Outstanding	4.57	Outstanding
Overall Mean	4.47	Outstanding	4.43	Outstanding

Table 30 shows the summary of the respondents' work performance level. Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers possess *outstanding* task and contextual performance, and their IPCRF KRA has an overall mean of 4.47 and 4.43, respectively.

Notably, the teachers' level of work performance along the task and contextual performance, work behavior, and the five Key Result Areas of their IPCRF were all rated *outstanding*. This affirms that during the new normal, even amidst the pandemic, teachers do perform their best to deliver meaningful teaching and learning for the benefit of learners. Truly, they deserve recognition for their act of heroism and for becoming the bridge for the learners to achieve their aspired dreams.

Indeed, teachers have to demonstrate exceptional performance despite the ever-challenging situations. This is asserted by Koopmans et al. (2014) that work performance is very important in determining consistency and maintaining employee work resilience.

Bobek (2002) contended that experienced teachers are a valuable resource for new teachers and may act as mentors for beginning teachers. She strongly encouraged mentoring programs for new teachers.

6. Significant Difference Between the Respondents' Level of Work Performance When Grouped According to Their Profile

a. Tech-Voc School Teachers

a.1 Age

Table 31. Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Tech-Voc School Teachers' Level of Work Performance When Grouped According to Their Age

Tech-Voc School Teachers' Age and the Following Work Performance	Probability of F	Decision	Remarks
a. Task Performance	0.00000045	Reject H ₀	Significant
b. Contextual Performance	0.00000039	Reject H ₀	Significant
c. Work Behavior	0.00000000	Reject H ₀	Significant
d. IPCRF: KRA 1	0.000000057	Reject H ₀	Significant
KRA 2	0.000000086	Reject H ₀	Significant
KRA 3	0.000000062	Reject H ₀	Significant
KRA 4	0.000000081	Reject H ₀	Significant
KRA 5	0.000000087	Reject H ₀	Significant

The results of the test of significant difference in the Tech-Voc School teachers' level of work performance when grouped according to their age are presented in Table 31.

The results reveal that the F-probability values are less than 0.05. For this reason, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 level of significance, thus, there is a significant difference in Tech-Voc School teachers' level of work performance when grouped according to their age. It implies that the teachers have varied level of work performance along task and contextual performance, work behavior, and their IPCRF along the five key results areas when clustered by age.

As indicated by the mean in Appendix C, the teachers who are aged 56-60 are more outstanding in task performance, work behavior, and IPCRF along the key result areas 2, 4, and 5. While the teachers of age 51-55, 41-45, and 51-60 are more outstanding in contextual performance, and key result areas 1 and 3, respectively.

Relative to these findings, Anand (2020) found out that respondents differ in job characteristics and work performance based on their age where 'F' values are significant for most of the job characteristics dimension viz., skill variety, task significance, and

feedback along with total job characteristics as well as all the three dimensions of work performance viz., task performance, contextual performance, and counterproductive work behavior.

a.2 Sex

Table 32. Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Tech-Voc School Teachers' Level of Work Performance When Grouped According to Their Sex

Tech-Voc School Teachers' Sex and the Following Work Performance	Probability of F	Decision	Remarks
a. Task Performance	0.00010895	Reject H ₀	Significant
b. Contextual Performance	0.00139500	Reject H ₀	Significant
c. Work Behavior	0.00118400	Reject H ₀	Significant
d. IPCRF: KRA 1	0.00169730	Reject H ₀	Significant
KRA 2	0.00115790	Reject H ₀	Significant
KRA 3	0.00196050	Reject H ₀	Significant
KRA 4	0.00018520	Reject H ₀	Significant
KRA 5	0.00147370	Reject H ₀	Significant

Table 32 presents the results of the test of significant differences in the Tech-Voc School teachers' level of work performance when grouped according to their sex.

The results reveal that the P-values of F are less than 0.05, hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at a 0.05 significance level, meaning that there is a significant difference in Tech-Voc School teachers' level of work performance when grouped according to their sex. It shows that the male teachers differ in their work performance along task and contextual performance, work behavior, and the five key result areas of IPCRF from that of the female teachers. It is noted that the female teachers are more outstanding in task performance, and the key results in areas 1, 2, 3, and 5, while male teachers are more outstanding in contextual performance, work behavior, and key results in Area 4.

This contradicts Gaffud's (2008) and Gatan's (2001) findings that teaching performance is not significantly associated with sex.

a.3 Civil Status

Table 33. Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Tech-Voc School Teachers' Level of Work Performance When Grouped According to Their Civil Status

Tech-Voc School Teachers' Civil Status and the Following Work Performance	Probability of F	Decision	Remarks
a. Task Performance	0.00011490	Reject H_0	Significant
b. Contextual Performance	0.00003608	Reject H_0	Significant
c. Work Behavior	0.00001341	Reject H_0	Significant
d. IPCRF: KRA 1	0.00005770	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 2	0.00011049	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 3	0.00006723	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 4	0.00009513	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 5	0.00010790	Reject H_0	Significant

The results of the test of significant difference in the Tech-Voc School teachers' level of work performance when grouped according to their civil status are presented in Table 33.

It is evident from the results that the P-values of F are less than 0.05. This signifies the rejection of the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance which implies that there is a significant difference in the Tech-Voc School teachers' level of work performance when grouped according to their civil status. The teachers have varied work performance levels along with task and contextual performance, work behavior, and the five key result areas of IPCRF when classified by civil status. As indicated by the mean in Appendix C, it further infers that the married teachers are more outstanding in all the areas of work performance.

The results negate Gaffud's (2008) and Gatan's (2001) findings that teaching performance is not significantly associated with civil status.

a.4 Highest Educational Attainment

Table 34. Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Tech-Voc School Teachers' Level of Work Performance When Grouped According to Their Highest Educational Attainment

Tech-Voc School Teachers' Highest Educational Attainment and the Following Work Performance	Probability of F	Decision	Remarks
a. Task Performance	0.0000	Reject H_0	Significant

b. Contextual Performance	0.0000	Reject H ₀	Significant
c. Work Behavior	0.0000	Reject H ₀	Significant
d. IPCRF: KRA 1	0.0000	Reject H ₀	Significant
KRA 2	0.0000	Reject H ₀	Significant
KRA 3	0.0000	Reject H ₀	Significant
KRA 4	0.0000	Reject H ₀	Significant
KRA 5	0.0000	Reject H ₀	Significant

Table 34 reflects the results of the test of significant differences in the Tech-Voc School teachers' level of work performance when grouped according to their highest educational attainment.

The results show that the F-probability values are less than 0.05 thereby rejecting the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. As a result, there is a significant difference in the Tech-Voc School teachers' level of work performance along task and contextual performance, work behavior, and the five key result areas of IPCRF when grouped according to highest educational attainment. As noted, teachers who are doctorate holders are more outstanding in all aspects of work performance.

Results affirm the findings of Anand (2020) that respondents differ in their job characteristics and work performance based on their educational qualifications/attainment.

a.5 Teaching Position

Table 35. Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Tech-Voc School Teachers' Level of Work Performance When Grouped According to Their Teaching Position

Tech-Voc School Teachers' Teaching Position and the Following Work Performance	Probability of F	Decision	Remarks
a. Task Performance	0.0000	Reject H ₀	Significant
b. Contextual Performance	0.0000	Reject H ₀	Significant
c. Work Behavior	0.0000	Reject H ₀	Significant
d. IPCRF: KRA 1	0.0000	Reject H ₀	Significant
KRA 2	0.0000	Reject H ₀	Significant
KRA 3	0.0000	Reject H ₀	Significant
KRA 4	0.0000	Reject H ₀	Significant
KRA 5	0.0000	Reject H ₀	Significant

The results of the test of significant difference in the Tech-Voc School teachers' level of work performance, when grouped according to their teaching position, are reflected in Table 35.

It is evident from the results that the F-probability values are less than 0.05, hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at a 0.05 significance level. Thus, there is a significant difference in the Tech-Voc School teachers' level of work performance when grouped according to their teaching position. It shows that the teachers have different work

performance levels along task and contextual performance, work behavior, and the five key result areas of IPCRF when clustered by their teaching position. As indicated by the mean in Appendix C, those with Master Teacher 2 positions are more outstanding in their work performance level along task and contextual performance and the five key result areas of IPCRF, while the master teachers 1 are more outstanding on their work performance along work behavior.

The results affirm Gaffud's (2008) finding that teachers' teaching performance is significantly associated with their position or classification as teachers.

a.6 Length of Service

Table 36. Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Tech-Voc School Teachers' Level of Work Performance When Grouped According to Their Length of Service

Tech-Voc School Teachers' Length of Service and the Following Work Performance	Probability of F	Decision	Remarks
a. Task Performance	0.00000039	Reject H_0	Significant
b. Contextual Performance	0.00000032	Reject H_0	Significant
c. Work Behavior	0.00000000	Reject H_0	Significant
d. IPCRF: KRA 1	0.00000042	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 2	0.00000067	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 3	0.00000048	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 4	0.00000061	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 5	0.00000065	Reject H_0	Significant

Table 36 discloses the results of the test of significant differences in the Tech-Voc School teachers' level of work performance when grouped according to their length of service.

The results reveal that the P-values of F are less than 0.05 which leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, there is a significant difference in the Tech-Voc School teachers' level of work performance when grouped according to their length of service. It indicates that the teachers perform differently in their work in terms of task and contextual performance, work behavior, and the five key result areas of IPCRF when they are categorized by their length of service. The teachers who have served for 16-20 years are more outstanding on task and contextual performance, while the teachers who worked for 26-30 years and 11-15 years have more outstanding work performance as to work behavior and the key result area 1, respectively. Teachers who have been in the service for 31-35 years have more outstanding work performance in terms of IPCRF along the key result areas 2, 3, 4, and 5.

The findings contradict Anand's (2020) conclusion that there is no significant difference in respondents' work performance based on their experience or the length rendered in service.

b. Non-Tech-Voc School Teachers

b.1 Age

Table 37. Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Non-Tech-Voc School Teachers' Level of Work Performance When Grouped According to Their Age

Non-Tech-Voc School Teachers' Age and the Following Work Performance	Probability of F	Decision	Remarks
a. Task Performance	0.0000	Reject H_0	Significant
b. Contextual Performance	0.0000	Reject H_0	Significant
c. Work Behavior	0.0000	Reject H_0	Significant
d. IPCRF: KRA 1	0.0000	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 2	0.0000	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 3	0.0000	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 4	0.0000	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 5	0.0000	Reject H_0	Significant

The results of the test of significant difference in the Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers' level of work performance when grouped according to their age are disclosed in Table 37.

It is evident from the table that the F-probability values are less than 0.05 which means the rejection of the null hypothesis at 0.05 significance level. Thus, there is a significant difference in the Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers' level of work performance when grouped according to their age. It shows that the teachers vary in their work performance level along task and contextual performance, work behavior, and the five key result areas of IPCRF when clustered by age. As evidenced by the mean in Appendix C, the teachers who are aged 21-25 have more outstanding work performance on contextual, and the key result areas 2 and 4 of IPCRF. Those of age 26-30 perform more outstandingly in key result area 1 whereas teachers whose age are 36-40 are more outstanding in their work performance on work behavior and key result area 5 of the IPCRF. Teachers who belong to the age bracket 41-45 perform more outstandingly in their work on task performance and the key result area 3 of IPCRF.

Results are related to that of Anand's (2020) findings that respondents differ in job characteristics and work performance based on their age where 'F' values are significant for most of the job characteristics dimension viz., skill variety, task significance, and feedback along with total job characteristics as well as all the three dimensions of work performance viz., task performance, contextual performance, and counterproductive work behavior.

b.2 Sex

Table 38. Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Non-Tech-Voc High School Teachers Level of Work Performance When Grouped According to Their Sex

Non-Tech-Voc High School Teachers' Sex and the Following Work Performance	Probability of F	Decision	Remarks
a. Task Performance	0.000098	Reject H_0	Significant
b. Contextual Performance	0.000760	Reject H_0	Significant
c. Work Behavior	0.001391	Reject H_0	Significant
d. IPCRF: KRA 1	0.000088	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 2	0.000227	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 3	0.000593	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 4	0.000048	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 5	0.000358	Reject H_0	Significant

Table 38 reveals the results of the test of significant differences in the Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers' level of work performance when grouped according to their sex.

The results reveal that the P-values of F are less than 0.05, hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at a 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is a significant difference in Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers' level of work performance when grouped according to their sex. It implies that the male teachers differ in their work performance level on task and contextual performance, work behavior, and the five key result areas of IPCRF from that of the female teachers. The study further shows that male teachers perform more outstandingly in their work along task and contextual performance, work behavior, and the key result areas 1, 2, 4, and 5 of IPCRF, while female teachers are more outstanding on key result area 3 of IPCRF.

This is in contrast with Gaffud's (2008) and Gatan's (2001) findings that teaching performance is not significantly associated with sex.

b.3 Civil Status

Table 39. Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Non-Tech-Voc High School Teachers' Level of Work Performance When Grouped According to Their Civil Status

Non-Tech-Voc High School Teachers' Civil Status and the Following Work Performance	Probability of F	Decision	Remarks
a. Task Performance	0.000028	Reject H_0	Significant
b. Contextual Performance	0.000013	Reject H_0	Significant
c. Work Behavior	0.000001	Reject H_0	Significant
d. IPCRF: KRA 1	0.000079	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 2	0.000068	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 3	0.000063	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 4	0.000071	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 5	0.000085	Reject H_0	Significant

The results of the test of significant difference in the Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers' level of work performance when grouped according to their civil status are presented in Table 39.

It is evident from the results that the probability values of F are less than 0.05. This signifies the rejection of the null hypothesis at a 0.05 significance level which means that there is a significant difference in the Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers' level of work performance when grouped according to their civil status. It shows that the teachers have varied work performance levels along task and contextual performance, work behavior, and the five key result areas of IPCRF when grouped by their civil status. As evidenced by the mean in Appendix C, the single teachers perform more outstandingly on task and contextual performance, and the five key result areas of IPCRF, while the married teachers are more outstanding on work behavior.

The results oppose Gaffud's (2008) and Gatan's (2001) findings which revealed that teaching performance is not significantly associated with civil status.

b.4 Highest Educational Attainment

Table 40. Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Non-Tech-Voc High School Teachers' Level of Work Performance When Grouped According to Their Highest Educational Attainment

Non-Tech-Voc High School Teachers' Highest Educational Attainment and the Following Work Performance	Probability of F	Decision	Remarks
a. Task Performance	0.0000	Reject H_0	Significant
b. Contextual Performance	0.0000	Reject H_0	Significant
c. Work Behavior	0.0000	Reject H_0	Significant
d. IPCRF: KRA 1	0.0000	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 2	0.0000	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 3	0.0000	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 4	0.0000	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 5	0.0000	Reject H_0	Significant

Table 40 reflects the results of the test of significant difference in the Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers' level of work performance when grouped according to their highest educational attainment.

The results reveal that the P-values of F are less than 0.05, hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at a 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is a significant difference in the Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers' level of work performance when grouped according to their highest educational attainment. It shows that the teachers have varied work performance levels on task and contextual performance, work behavior, and the five key result areas of IPCRF when categorized by their highest educational attainment. As appended, teachers who are bachelor's degree holders are more outstanding in their performance on work behavior, contextual performance, and the key result area 1 of the

IPCRF, while those who are master's degree holders perform more outstandingly in their work along task performance, and the key result areas 2, 3, and 4 of IPCRF. The doctorate holders are more outstanding in their work performance on work behavior and the key result area 5 of the IPCRF.

The study's findings affirm Anand's (2020) conclusion that respondents differ in job characteristics and work performance based on their educational qualifications.

b.5 Teaching Position

Table 41. Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Non-Tech-Voc High School Teachers' Level of Work Performance When Grouped According to Teaching Position

Non-Tech-Voc High School Teachers' Teaching Position and the Following Work Performance	Probability of F	Decision	Remarks
a. Task Performance	0.0000	Reject H_0	Significant
b. Contextual Performance	0.0000	Reject H_0	Significant
c. Work Behavior	0.0000	Reject H_0	Significant
d. IPCRF: KRA 1	0.0000	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 2	0.0000	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 3	0.0000	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 4	0.0000	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 5	0.0000	Reject H_0	Significant

The results of the test of significant difference in the Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers' level of work performance when grouped according to their teaching position are reflected in Table 41.

It is evident from the results that the probability F-values are less than 0.05. This signifies the rejection of the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance, hence, there is a significant difference in the Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers' level of work performance when grouped according to their teaching position. The teachers have different work performance levels on task and contextual performance, work behavior, and the five key result areas of IPCRF. Those who hold the Teacher 2 position are more outstanding on task and contextual performance, and the key result areas 1, 2, 3, and 5 of IPCRF, while those with Teacher 1 and Teacher 3 positions perform more outstandingly in their work along key result area 4 of IPCRF, and work behavior, respectively.

The results relate to Gaffud's (2008) finding that teachers' teaching performance is significantly associated with their position or classification as teachers.

b.6 Length of Service

Table 42. Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Non-Tech-Voc High School Teachers' Level of Work Performance When Grouped According to Length of Service

Non-Tech-Voc High School Teachers' Length of Service and the Following Work Performance	Probability of F	Decision	Remarks
a. Task Performance	0.00000002	Reject H_0	Significant
b. Contextual Performance	0.00000001	Reject H_0	Significant
c. Work Behavior	0.00000000	Reject H_0	Significant
d. IPCRF: KRA 1	0.00000002	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 2	0.00000003	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 3	0.00000003	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 4	0.00000002	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 5	0.00000004	Reject H_0	Significant

Table 42 exhibits the results of the test of significant difference in the Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers' level of work performance when grouped according to their length of service.

The results show that the P-values of F are less than 0.05. For this reason, the null hypothesis is rejected at a 0.05 significance level, meaning, there is a significant difference in the Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers' level of work performance when grouped according to their length of service. It implies that the teachers differ from each other in their work performance level on task and contextual performance, work behavior, and the five key result areas of IPCRF when classified by their length of service. The teachers who have taught for 11-15 years perform more outstandingly on task and contextual performance, and the key result areas 4 and 5 of IPCRF. Those who have served for 1-5 years are more outstanding on the key result areas 1, 2, and 3 of IPCRF, whereas the teachers who have worked for 36-40 years are more outstanding on work behavior.

These results differ from that of Anand's (2020) findings that there is no significant difference in respondents' work performance based on their *experience* or the length rendered in the service.

7. Significant Difference Between Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc School Teachers' Level of Work Performance

Table 43. Results of the Test of Significant Difference in the Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc School Teachers' Level of Work Performance

Work Performance	Mean		Probability of t	Decision	Remarks
	Tech-Voc School Teachers	Non-Tech-Voc High School Teachers			
a. Task Performance	4.40	4.42	0.6741	Accept H_0	Not Significant

b. Contextual Performance	4.29	4.30	0.9815	Accept H ₀	Not Significant
c. Work Behavior	1.61	1.57	0.5675	Accept H ₀	Not Significant
d. IPCRF: KRA 1	4.59	4.61	0.6336	Accept H ₀	Not Significant
KRA 2	4.81	4.71	0.0174	Reject H ₀	Significant
KRA 3	4.62	4.62	0.9518	Accept H ₀	Not Significant
KRA 4	4.75	4.73	0.6710	Accept H ₀	Not Significant
KRA 5	4.80	4.79	0.7256	Accept H ₀	Not Significant

The results of the test of significant difference in the Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc School teachers' level of work performance are disclosed in Table 43.

It is revealed that the t-probability values are greater than 0.05 except for the key result area 2. This signifies the acceptance of the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance, therefore, there is no significant difference in the Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers' level of work performance along task and contextual performance, work behavior, and the key result areas 1, 3, 4, and 5 of IPCRF. It indicates that the two groups of teachers do not differ from each other in their work performance levels in the aforementioned areas. It states further that the two groups of teachers have similar work performance levels in the said areas.

However, there is a significant difference in the Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers' level of work performance on the key result area 2 of their IPCRF which is on Learning Environment. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at a 0.05 significance level. It implies that the two groups of teachers vary in their work performance level in terms of Learning Environment, key result area 2 in their IPCRF. It further shows that the Tech-Voc Teachers perform better in their work performance on KRA 2 than the Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers.

The current study shows no difference in work performance among groups of respondents. They both highly perform in their work. Relative to this, Baluyos, Rivera, and Baluyos (2019) revealed that the teachers are highly satisfied with their job and their work performance is very satisfactory.

8. Significant Relationship Between the Respondents' Resilience and Their Work Performance

a. Tech-Voc School Teachers

a.1 Personal Competencies and Persistence versus Work Performance

Table 44. Results of the Test of Significant Relationship Between the Tech-Voc School Teachers' Resilience in Terms of Personal Competencies and Persistence and their Work Performance

Tech-Voc School Teachers' Resilience in Terms of Personal Competencies and Persistence and the Following Work Performance	Probability of r	Decision	Remarks
a. Task Performance	0.00000000	Reject H ₀	Significant
b. Contextual Performance	0.00000000	Reject H ₀	Significant
c. Work Behavior	0.00000040	Reject H ₀	Significant
d. IPCRF: KRA 1	0.00000300	Reject H ₀	Significant
KRA 2	0.00000050	Reject H ₀	Significant
KRA 3	0.00002380	Reject H ₀	Significant
KRA 4	0.00000043	Reject H ₀	Significant
KRA 5	0.00001180	Reject H ₀	Significant

The results of the test of a significant relationship between the Tech-Voc School teachers' resilience in terms of personal competencies and persistence and their work performance are exhibited in Table 44.

It is evident from the results that the r-probability values are less than 0.05, hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at a 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is a significant relationship between the Tech-Voc School teachers' resilience in terms of personal competencies and persistence and their work performance. It shows that the teachers' resilience in personal competencies and persistence strongly affect their task and contextual performance, work behavior, and the five key result areas of IPCRF.

Teachers' level of resilience is optimum despite the challenging situation they are facing during the new normal. In relation to this, Gibbs and Miller (2014) contended that lecturers are resilient and there should not be too much worry about their commitment to their teaching. They are very likely to be able to adapt to the new teaching situation.

a.2 Family Cohesion versus Work Performance

Table 45. Results of the Test of Significant Relationship Between the Tech-Voc School Teachers' Resilience in Terms of Family Cohesion and their Work Performance

Tech-Voc School Teachers' Resilience in Terms of Family Cohesion and the Following Work Performance	Probability of r	Decision	Remarks
a. Task Performance	0.00000004	Reject H ₀	Significant
b. Contextual Performance	0.00002910	Reject H ₀	Significant
c. Work Behavior	0.00002616	Reject H ₀	Significant
d. IPCRF: KRA 1	0.00062120	Reject H ₀	Significant
KRA 2	0.00000665	Reject H ₀	Significant
KRA 3	0.00115000	Reject H ₀	Significant
KRA 4	0.00064635	Reject H ₀	Significant
KRA 5	0.00676200	Reject H ₀	Significant

Table 45 presents the results of the test of a significant relationship between the Tech-Voc School teachers' resilience in terms of family cohesion and their work performance.

The results reflect that the P-values of r are less than 0.05 which signifies the rejection of the null hypothesis at 0.05 significance level. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between the Tech-Voc School teachers' resilience in terms of family cohesion and their work performance. It indicates that the family cohesion resilience of the teachers has a strong effect on their work performance on task and contextual performance, work behavior, and the five key result areas of their IPCRF.

Strong family connection helps individuals maintain their resilience in their work. Drew and Sosnowski (2019) recount that teachers use relationships with colleagues, students, and school leaders to endure challenges. Hence, better teaching performance is carried out.

a.3 Social Skills and Peer Support versus Work Performance

Table 46. Results of the Test of Significant Relationship Between the Tech-Voc School Teachers'

Tech-Voc School Teachers' Resilience in Terms of Social Skills and Peer Support and the Following Work Performance	Probability of r	Decision	Remarks
a. Task Performance	0.00000000	Reject H_0	Significant
b. Contextual Performance	0.00000000	Reject H_0	Significant
c. Work Behavior	0.01485500	Reject H_0	Significant
d. IPCRF: KRA 1	0.00019580	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 2	0.00112922	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 3	0.02100170	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 4	0.01269000	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 5	0.00316070	Reject H_0	Significant

The results of the test of a significant relationship between the Tech-Voc School teachers' resilience in terms of social skills and peer support and their work performance are presented in Table 46.

It is revealed from the results that the r-probability values are less than 0.05 which leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. As a result, there is a significant relationship between the Tech-Voc School teachers' resilience in terms of social skills and peer support and their work performance. It shows that the teachers' work performance on task and contextual performance, work behavior, and the five key result areas of their IPCRF are strongly affected by their social skills and peer support resilience.

Peer support is vital to every individual in maintaining resilience and good work performance. Luthar (2006) affirms that resilience is the product of healthy relationships

between coworkers. Accordingly, Stuart et al. (2012) found a noteworthy relationship between resilient teachers and effective teaching.

a.4 Spiritual Influences versus Work Performance

Table 47. Results of the Test of Significant Relationship Between the Tech-Voc School Teachers' Resilience in Terms of Spiritual Influences and their Work Performance

Tech-Voc School Teachers' Resilience in Terms of Spiritual Influences and the Following Work Performance	Probability of r	Decision	Remarks
a. Task Performance	0.00000087	Reject H ₀	Significant
b. Contextual Performance	0.00000591	Reject H ₀	Significant
c. Work Behavior	0.00024720	Reject H ₀	Significant
d. IPCRF: KRA 1	0.00000005	Reject H ₀	Significant
KRA 2	0.00060330	Reject H ₀	Significant
KRA 3	0.00027200	Reject H ₀	Significant
KRA 4	0.00042710	Reject H ₀	Significant
KRA 5	0.00820300	Reject H ₀	Significant

Table 47 exhibits the results of the test of a significant relationship between the Tech-Voc School teachers' resilience in terms of spiritual influences and their work performance.

The results reveal that the P-values of r are less than 0.05. For this reason, the null hypothesis is rejected at a 0.05 significance level. As a result, there is a significant relationship between the Tech-Voc School teachers' resilience in terms of spiritual influences and their work performance. It states that the work performance of the teachers along with task and contextual performance, work behavior, and the five key result areas of their IPCRF are strongly influenced by their spiritual resilience.

Spirituality allows individuals to be resilient even in times of extreme life challenges. Drew and Sosnowski (2019) claimed that if a teacher is resilient, despite ever-changing contexts and situations where he or she works, the teacher is likely to be able to maintain his/her quality teaching performance. Steffy, et al.(2000) concluded that resilient teachers exhibit characteristics that are positive, professional, and reflective, in their teaching careers.

b. Non-Tech-Voc School Teachers

b.1 Personal Competencies and Persistence versus Work Performance

Table 48. Results of the Test of Significant Relationship Between the Non-Tech-Voc School Teachers' Resilience in Terms of Personal Competencies and Persistence and their Work Performance

Non-Tech-Voc School Teachers' Resilience in Terms of Personal Competencies and	Probability of r	Decision	Remarks
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Persistence and the Following Work Performance			
a. Task Performance	0.00000000	Reject H ₀	Significant
b. Contextual Performance	0.00003000	Reject H ₀	Significant
c. Work Behavior	0.01928000	Reject H ₀	Significant
d. IPCRF: KRA 1	0.00042240	Reject H ₀	Significant
KRA 2	0.01486000	Reject H ₀	Significant
KRA 3	0.00000000	Reject H ₀	Significant
KRA 4	0.01634400	Reject H ₀	Significant
KRA 5	0.00010780	Reject H ₀	Significant

The results of the test of a significant relationship between the Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers' resilience in terms of personal competencies and persistence and their work performance are exhibited in Table 48.

It is reflected from the results that the r-probability values are less than 0.05, hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at a 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is a significant relationship between the Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers' resilience in terms of personal competencies and persistence and their work performance. It shows that the teachers' work performance along the task and contextual performance, work behavior, and the five key result areas of IPCRF are strongly affected by their resilience in personal competencies and persistence.

Relatively, Gibbs and Miller (2014) conveyed that there is a need to ensure that teachers are resilient as this quality in teachers is central to well-motivated, consistent, and effective teaching.

b.2 Family Cohesion versus Work Performance

Table 49. Results of the Test of Significant Relationship Between the Non-Tech-Voc High School Teachers' Resilience in Terms of Family Cohesion and their Work Performance

Non-Tech-Voc High School Teachers' Resilience in Terms of Family Cohesion and the Following Work Performance	Probability of r	Decision	Remarks
a. Task Performance	0.00048000	Reject H ₀	Significant
b. Contextual Performance	0.03013900	Reject H ₀	Significant
c. Work Behavior	0.01455900	Reject H ₀	Significant
d. IPCRF: KRA 1	0.01078800	Reject H ₀	Significant
KRA 2	0.00748900	Reject H ₀	Significant
KRA 3	0.00000000	Reject H ₀	Significant
KRA 4	0.04419000	Reject H ₀	Significant
KRA 5	0.00062040	Reject H ₀	Significant

Table 49 discloses the results of the test of a significant relationship between the Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers' resilience in terms of family cohesion and their work performance.

The results show that the probability values of r are less than 0.05 signifying the rejection of the null hypothesis at 0.05 significance level. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between the Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers' resilience in terms of family cohesion and their work performance. The teachers' family cohesion resilience has a strong bearing on their work performance along with task and contextual performance, work behavior, and the five key result areas of their IPCRF.

Strong family ties benefit individuals to further maintain their resilience, especially in their work. Drew and Sosnowski (2019) relate that teachers use relationships with colleagues, students, and school leaders to endure challenges. Hence, better teaching performance is carried out.

b.3 Social Skills and Peer Support versus Work Performance

Table 50. Results of the Test of Significant Relationship Between the Non-Tech-Voc High School Teachers' Resilience in Terms of Social Skills and Peer Support and their Work Performance

Non-Tech-Voc High School Teachers' Resilience in Terms of Social Skills and Peer Support and the Following Work Performance	Probability of r	Decision	Remarks
a. Task Performance	0.00000000	Reject H_0	Significant
b. Contextual Performance	0.00000000	Reject H_0	Significant
c. Work Behavior	0.00000400	Reject H_0	Significant
d. IPCRF: KRA 1	0.00000200	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 2	0.00000400	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 3	0.00000000	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 4	0.00036000	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 5	0.00012900	Reject H_0	Significant

The results of the test of a significant relationship between the Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers' resilience in terms of social skills and peer support and their work performance are disclosed in Table 50.

The table shows that the P-values of r are less than 0.05 which means that the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 level of significance. As a result, there is a significant relationship between the Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers' resilience in terms of social skills and peer support and their work performance. It indicates that the teachers' social skills and peer support strongly affect their task and contextual performance, work behavior, and the five key result areas of their IPCRF.

Botou et al. (2017) confirm that positive relationships with colleagues help teachers maintain their resilience during the economic crisis. Lippman and Schmitz (2013) noted in their research investigation that teachers with a high degree of resiliency will boost school performance. The greater the teacher's resiliency, the more dedicated he or she becomes to direct his or her efforts toward school-wide changes, considering the many demands of his or her job. This, too, may affect teachers' work performance.

b.4 Spiritual Influences versus Work Performance

Table 51. Results of the Test of Significant Relationship Between the Non-Tech-Voc High School Teachers' Resilience in Terms of Spiritual Influences and their Work Performance

Non-Tech-Voc High School Teachers' Resilience in Terms of Spiritual Influences and the Following Work Performance	Probability of r	Decision	Remarks
a. Task Performance	0.00000110	Reject H_0	Significant
b. Contextual Performance	0.00134000	Reject H_0	Significant
c. Work Behavior	0.02848000	Reject H_0	Significant
d. IPCRF: KRA 1	0.00032240	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 2	0.00000000	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 3	0.00000306	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 4	0.00000000	Reject H_0	Significant
KRA 5	0.00000000	Reject H_0	Significant

Table 51 presents the results of the test of the significant relationship between the Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers' resilience in terms of spiritual influences and their work performance.

The results show that the r-probability values are less than 0.05, hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is a significant relationship between the Non-Tech-Voc High School teachers' resilience in terms of spiritual influences and their work performance. It implies that the teachers' task and contextual performance, work behavior, and the five key result areas of their IPCRF are strongly influenced by their spiritual resilience.

Strong faith helps individuals gain resilience even in hard situations. Bobek (2002) emphasized the promotion of teacher resiliency to enhance teacher effectiveness, heighten teacher satisfaction, and better prepare teachers to adjust to education's ever-changing conditions. Furthermore, Sutriyantono & Rubin (2013) concluded that teachers' performance is improved through attitude modification, work motivation, and favorable organizational culture in schools.

This study reveals that resilience is associated with work performance, hence, the need to elevate and strengthen teachers' resilience for them to keep an excellent teaching performance. Such a result affirms Fonte et al.'s (2021) findings that there is a significant relationship between the level of resilience and the work performance of public secondary school teachers, therefore, resilience affects teachers' work performance. When teachers demonstrate a high level of resilience, better teaching performance is expected. In addition, Greenfield (2015) and Mansfield et al. (2016) disclosed that teacher resilience is related to teacher self-efficacy, job satisfaction, teacher effectiveness, and motivation. Similarly, Koopmans et al. (2014) found out that work performance is very important in determining consistency and maintaining employee work resilience. Finally, Briner &

Dewberry (2007) indicate that improving school performance has a positive impact on school wellbeing, and improving teacher wellbeing also improves student outcomes.

Conclusions

This study concludes that most of the Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc teachers are middle-aged, predominantly female, married, possess master's units, and have relatively short tenures. The respondents demonstrate high personal competencies and persistence, exhibiting very high levels of resilience in family cohesion, social skills and peer support, and spiritual influences. Notably, the level of resilience among Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc teachers significantly varies based on their profile. While their resilience differs in personal competencies and persistence, it does not vary in terms of family cohesion, social skills peer support, and spiritual influences. Both groups of teachers exhibit outstanding work performance in task and contextual performance, work behavior, and all key results areas of their Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF).

The study also finds that work performance is significantly influenced by age, sex, civil status, educational background, position, and years in service. Variations in work performance are observed in IPCRF Key Result Area (KRA) 2, whereas similarities are noted in task and contextual performance, work behavior, and KRAs 1, 3, 4, and 5 of the IPCRF. Additionally, Tech-Voc and Non-Tech-Voc teachers perform exceptionally well in their primary teaching roles, extra responsibilities, attitudes towards work, and various KRAs of the IPCRF, which encompass Content Knowledge and Pedagogy, Diversity of Learners, Curriculum and Planning, Assessment and Reporting, Community Linkages and Professional Engagement, and Personal Growth and Professional Development, as well as the Plus Factor. However, their performance is not outstanding in the area of the Learning Environment.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion drawn, the study recommends the following:

1. Teachers' resilience should always be sustained through genuine care and support of the school administration especially the department to always look after their general welfare since they are the educational frontline in the system and are the prime movers of the educative process.
2. Seasoned teachers, especially the master teachers should provide technical assistance and become coaches and mentors to the novice teachers to share their expertise and their best classroom practices to enhance their work performance.
3. Teachers are encouraged to attend capacity-building seminars or related trainings to elevate, strengthen, and sustain a high resilience level since it is a significant factor that influences teachers' professional performance.

4. The proposed learning and development program for teachers should be reviewed, considered, and implemented to ensure a very high level of resilience and outstanding work performance among educators.
 5. Further studies can be carried out to look into other factors associated with resilience impacting instructional performance.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

As the author of this study, I declare my adherence to ethical standards. Informed consent was obtained, and respondents could withdraw at any time. Anonymity was maintained, and their well-being was safeguarded. There were no conflicts of interest, and plagiarism was strictly avoided. I ensured an unbiased interpretation of the findings, and the results were intended solely for research purposes.

Acknowledgments

I am deeply grateful to my research adviser for her expert guidance and encouragement. Sincere thanks to the respondents for their participation, and to my colleagues for their support. My heartfelt appreciation goes to my family, friends, and relatives for their constant encouragement. Above all, I thank God for the strength and wisdom to complete this research.

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